

ZURO

1976

*The Magazine of the History Society
Umtali Boys' High School*

ZURO 1976.

No. 9

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Editorial.

It seems paradoxical that a science student studying four straight science subjects should be writing an editorial for a history magazine. Equally amazing is the fact that four of the five members of this year's History Society committee are scientists. Of what possible benefit can history and a History Society be to a science student?

Firstly, history is an excellent subject for broadening one's horizons. Scientists tend to be insular and narrow minded, knowing that to achieve anything worthwhile one must be specific. Today a detailed study of one aspect is believed to be considerably more valuable than a vague knowledge of many. Thus although the Sciences are extremely valuable for developing the thought processes of an individual they do not encourage a wider knowledge of the many other facets of life. History achieves this in a way that no other subject can.

Secondly history is important to the science student in his own field. History is a subject which encourages analysis of given facts, and their subsequent use to substantiate an opinion. It requires logical thought and clear expression of an argument. All these abilities are extremely useful to the scientist - someone who constantly has to interpret experimental data.

Personally I regret the necessity of giving up history after 'O' Level. Hence the great value to me - and I believe to all science students in a similar position - of a History Society by which I can maintain my interest in the subject.

H. Ball.

Chairman's Report.

The Society has enjoyed another successful year despite difficulties arising from the current security situation. Paid-up membership has remained high.

It is unfortunate that this year we had only four speakers compared to the five in 1975. Our speakers included Dr. A. Spector who gave an illustrated account of the American Indian culture and Mr. C.K. Cooke of the National Museums and Monuments who gave a slide show on Rhodesian Rock Art. Also from the Museums, Dr. T. Huffman lectured on Manicaland's Iron Age while Mr. A. Kuwadza of the Department of African Education delivered an address on Shona customs. The quality of these lectures certainly made up for diminished quantity. In defence of the committee I must add that over ten speakers were approached but the response was disappointing.

I must express my thanks to Marymount for allowing us their hall as a venue for some of these talks. This year the society has been in close liason with Marymount and some of our members have attended regularly their Archaeology Club which was run on a weekly basis.

Our field-work was sharply reduced this year for security reasons but members did enjoy a profitable weeked at Tanda TTL in the first term. We surveyed and mapped a newly discovered ruin and then visited other local ruins and rock paintings on the return trip. The resulting report and map received the thanks of National Museums and Monuments and will be published in the Rhodesian Prehistory magazine in December.

In the third term our only outing was to the Finger Rock Shelter on St. Augustine's Farm. The purpose was to locate and record the site and its contents to help with the national survey being conducted by the Museums.

During the course of the year the society's archivist, J. Harris, set up some interesting displays in the school foyer. My thanks must go to the whole committee for performing a competent task so enthusiastically. Felicity West, as UGHS representative, provided contact with the girls' school, T. Carroll worked hard as secretary and P. Nicholas successfully kept our debts to a minimum. H. Ball has worked determindly to collect and edit material for Zuro.

However above all, the society is indebted to our President, Mr. Barnes, for providing a source of inspiration and enthusiasm. His departure to South Africa will be a loss to this school and to this society in particular. I would like to thank him for his personal contribution to the running of this society and to wish him and his wife every success in the future.

Although the functions of the society will have to adapt to the security situation, I would appeal to returning members not to allow this to thwart their enthusiasm. I am confident that the society will continue to thrive and, on behalf of retiring members, I wish the society a prosperous future.

R. Plowes.

Treasurer's Report.

<u>Credit.</u>		<u>Debit</u>	
Subscriptions	32.00	Tanda Trip	10.00
Donations:		O Level History Prize	5.00
Mrs. Izzett	2.00	Est. cost Zuro	10.00
Mr. Ford	2.50		
Est. income Zuro	5.00		
	<u>\$ 41.50</u>		<u>\$ 25.00</u>

Excess Income over Expenditure: \$16.50.

Once again our income exceeds expenditure despite the fact that this year the society did not show a film.

The number of members has increased - 64 paid-up members this year - and I am most grateful to Felicity West for increasing our UGHS membership.

Mention must be made of the generous donations from our two honorary members, Mrs. P.Izzett and Mr.J.Ford; we are most grateful for their interest in the society.

P.Nicholas.

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Paid-up Membership, 1976.U.B.H.S.

Arthur
Bainbridge
Baker
Bentley
Bowler M.C.
Bowler M.P.
Bradford L.
Carroll T.
Catsicas J.
Catsicas P.
Christophedes
Coventry
de Klerk P
de Kock
Flower K.
Flower M.
Forrester R.
George
Grispos
Harris
Heyne

Johnston
Latham
Marais
Martin.
McLelland
Mennell
Moore
More
Nicholas
Nortje
Olsen
Paget
Papini
Plowes
Ranby
Rault
Richter
Sher
Thomas D.
Thomas S.
Thorne
Van der Meeburg

Van de Ruit
Williams
Wilson
Witt
Wylie
Zorn
U.G.H.S.
D.Ashburner
G.Barry
J.Broster
J.Evans
M.Field
F.Heath-Stubbs
D.Heyter
D.Latham
J.Latham
P.Mellor
L.Mungle
P.Poggioli
D.Scruton
T.Swift
F.West

.....

The History Society Prize for the best O Level results in the 'mock' examinations went to F.Bradford of 4A1.

The prize has been awarded annually since 1970. It is interesting to note that of the previous recipients, three (P.Walsh, R.Plowes and H.Ball) have later been elected Chairman of the History Society.

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Minutes of a Meeting of the History Society, 12th February.The Origins of the American Red Indian.

Dr. A. Spector.

The typical concept of a Red Indian is a bronzed man on horseback shooting with a bow and arrow, cutting off scalps and being chased by cowboys. This is a very narrow picture confined to the 19th and typifying only the war-like plains Indian of the south-west as romanticised by Hollywood. It neglects thousands of years of history.

In 1492 Columbus sought a new route to India by sailing west. On reaching land he thought he had discovered India, hence the misnomer, 'Indian'. The initial reaction was that these Indians were sub-human, but the Pope declared that as all men were descended from Adam and Eve they were part of the human race. The subsequent theory, still held by some people today, was that they were part of the lost tribe of Israel and had been transported to America by the devil! It was also suggested that they had come from the lost continent, Atlantis.

An American Jesuit missionary was the first to suggest that they must have come by a land-crossing from the old world. This was some 120 years before Baring discovered the Straights that bear his name; a sea-passage was rejected because it would not explain how the animals crossed over. It was an Englishman who first suggested that they were descended from the Tartars of north-eastern and central Asia.

Scientific investigation has supported this theory. For example, both races have a dusty brown skin, the Indians never have blue or hazel eyes but, like the Mongols, only brown; both have prominent cheek bones and coarse, straight black hair on the head although body hair is sparse. But the clinching factor is the 'shovel incisor' - the inside front teeth are scooped forward. The incidence between Indian and Mongol is 90% compared to only 15% between other world races. This explains where he came from, but not how he came.

The answer is linked to the American glacial periods. A skull was discovered near Los Angeles and dated to 23 600 years ago together with artifacts dating back 28 000 years. The skull was that of modern man who did not emerge until 40 000 BC. Yet the crossing must have been made by modern man - only he had the intelligence to do it. Thus it must have been accomplished sometime between 28 000 and 40 000 years ago.

There were three glacial periods which provided a land bridge between America and Asia. The third and most recent (13 - 20 000 BC) covered all of north Canada but the earlier two (20 - 28 000 and 32 - 36 000) left a corridor from north-west Canada through to central America. The dates of the skull thus determine the dates of the crossing ie 32 000 - 36 000 years ago. It is reasoned that the glaciers took up moisture and therefore dropped the sea level so that the 60 mile gap across the Baring Straights was in fact a land bridge. Being a hunter-cum-gatherer the Indian stayed close to the herds and as the animals migrated so did he follow their path.

Two apparent discrepancies to this theory are that the Indian, unlike the Mongol, has a hawk-like nose whilst the Mongol has a fleshy eye-lid. The answer is that these

characteristics developed after the crossing had been made. Proof comes in the form of the Eskimos and Aleuts who were more recent immigrants to America and have the same eyelids and nose of the Mongols.

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Minutes of a Meeting of the History Society, 11th March.

Rock Art.

Mr. C.K. Cooke.

Rock art is man's first recorded expression of his feelings. In Europe there is evidence of sympathetic magic, eg. hunting scenes depicting animals with arrows and spears in them. This may be the case in Rhodesia, although there is no conclusive evidence.

By examining the supposition of paintings (ie the placement of one over the other) it is possible to detect six different periods or styles.

I. This is too advanced to have been the earliest period. It is crude but the animals are recognisable although they are box-like, lacking in character and painted all in one colour. The human figures are simple, match stick figures barely recognisable but for the fat buttocks of the Bushmen. It is possible to distinguish between male and female.

II. Animals are shown in a variety of positions with an increased sense of movement. The technique has changed too in that an outline is drawn first and filled in with 'mastic' (possibly euphorbia latex) and then the painting is done on top of this presenting a hard surface. Every type of antelope is depicted together with antbears, flying ants, hares, porcupines, mice, locusts, in fact anything edible! It even includes one possibly extinct species - the quagga.

The animals are in groups and trees and rocks are shown. The human figures are still stylised, and are probably Bushman. Mr. Cooke labels it the 'Classical Style.'

III. Outlines only drawn but human figures become more recognisable. The theory is that the painters saw strange beings (Hottentots?) with huts, sheep and staves and thus wished to record them. Animals are shown in different positions but it becomes more than just something to eat; eg. at the White Rhino Shelter the paintings distinguish between the black and white rhino. Incidentally it was this which prompted National Parks to re-introduce rhino into what had obviously been a suitable habitat.

It must have taken considerable skill to manipulate a continuous brush stroke on rough granite. There may have been some preliminary drawing in charcoal or iron oxide crayon.

IV. It is this period that we see most of today. White had been introduced into the pigments although unfortunately it often disappears and makes the surface rather powdery and similar to chalk.

The art is rather hurried - was this a disturbed period of life, eg. the arrival of the Iron Age people? We see

domesticated animals - horned and thick-tailed sheep. The paintings stretch from the Mtoko area through to Botswana, the S.W.Cape and east along the Cape coast - was this the line of Hottentot migration?

The sheep are usually accompanied by figures wearing cloaks and hats and apparently herdsmen in that they carry staves rather than spears. The Hottentot is drawn as a Causian type of Bushman with protruding stomach and buttocks, peppercorn hair and incurving spine.

At the same time scenes were painted: trees, leaves, roots, fish and birds - batleur eagles, pigeons, European and Adnam storks, swallows, francolin and guinea fowl.

V. Sometimes peculiar patterns are introduced - are they shelters, rocks, shields, an aerial view from a high cave of early agricultural efforts? At Diana's Vow we see typically negroid features together with a dog on a leash.

VI. Very crude, possibly drawn by Bantu whilst sheltering from raiders. They show no originality and stretch all over Rhodesia although more to the north of us than to the south.

It is interesting that there are no paintings of cattle either in Rhodesia or Zambia whilst there are in Egypt, Ethiopia, Tanganyika, N.Malawi and South Africa, all of which are humped.

Pigments

Red	-	haemetite, which heated became orange.
Yellow	-	limonite.
Purplish-reds	-	manganese
White	-	kaolin clay, limestone, ash or bird droppings.

It is not known what makes the paint stick; it could be latex of euphorbia, urine, egg yolk or white, fat or bone marrow.

Age.

Difficult to assess in that the evidence is circumstantial. An intelligent guess is required. Certainly those in South Africa begin and end later than those in Rhodesia. They are probably late stone age; the earliest could be 10 000 years old. And the latest show Ndebele shields!

Future Research.

There are many aspects still to be investigated, eg.

- . an ecological study based on animal distribution. eg. kudu appear everywhere but giraffe and rhino in suitable habitats only.
- . weapons used, eg. from simple arrows to compound arrows with feathers; shields and spears.
- . it might eventually be possible to work out migration routes.
- . clothing and headgear.
- . ceremonies.

Copying of Paintings.

This is a laborious but rewarding task: one copy may take four or five visits to a cave. The method is to put cellophane over one section of the cave and trace the paintings using

either a mixture of water colour and soap or chinograph pencils. This is then transferred to paper preferably with a granite-type background. The paintings are difficult to photograph because curvature of the rock causes distortion.

Also needed is the exact pinpointing of sites with a 6 figure reference on 1:50 000 O.S. maps, with a brief summary of what is at that particular site.

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Minutes of a Meeting of the History Society, 23rd March.

The Iron Age in Manicaland. Dr. T.N.Huffman.

Very basically the Iron Age in Southern Africa lasted about 2 000 years; there were two periods - Early and Late - each of which was about 1000 years in length. Because these periods coincided with population changes they have cultural connotations as well.

At the time of Christ there was a mass movement of people into Southern Africa, bringing with them a different life style, the typical aspects of which were:

- . semi-permanent villages of pole-and-daga huts;
- . an ability to smelt iron as evidenced by the remains of furnaces and forges, of iron slag and implements;
- . an ability of make clay pots with different sizes and shapes for different functions;
- . the above two suggest that these people were agriculturists rather than pastoralists. The largest pots were made to hold beer; moreover carbonised seed has been found and, in Tzaneen, seed impressions of a species of millet were found in pot clay;
- . 30 semi-complete skeletons have been recovered from Early Iron Age sites all of which are negroid, not Hottentot as thought earlier;
- . they domesticated animals as evidenced from the skeletal remains of sheep and goats;
- . in the north and eastern parts of Rhodesia are found as well figurines, normally about 100 in a midden some 15 metres from the village. These Early Iron Age figurines are of the female figure and have intense body decoration; it is presumed that they are associated with some form of initiation ceremony.

These people, who were Bantu speaking, originated in West Africa and came down the eastern side of Africa spreading out south of the equator.

At this point Dr. Huffman introduced two concepts:

- (a) the phase concept - people seem to exist for a period of time without change but when that change does come it is relatively sudden. Such stable periods are called phases and in this part of the world seem to last between 200 and 300 years. Ceramics, the decoration of which is idiosyncratic - ie. influenced by background and tradition and is non-functional - tend to be consistent throughout a phase.
- (b) culture - patterned, typical behaviour in which people tend to repeat the same activity.

To Show the Manica Iron Age in Relation to Other Rhodesian Phases.

Adapted from a Diagram by Dr. Huffman as published in Rhodesian Prehistory No 11, Dec. 1973, p.5

Early Iron Age villages, which tend to be large and located near water courses, often at the base of a hill, have been found at Chiredzi, Leopard's Kopje, the van Niekerk Ruins (not the ruins themselves,) Great Zimbabwe and Salisbury.

The first three phases encompassed the years 200 - 1000 AD but in c.1000 a new group appeared in Matabeleland which was ultimately to obliterate the previous culture. These later Iron Age people, known as the Leopard's Kopje Culture, and probably the first Shona speakers, are typified by mass burials. Their remains have been found in the central area of Salisbury, Matabeleland, Great Zimbabwe and Mt. Darwin but it is not known just how far east they spread.

We know that there was settlement in Manicaland after the C14th because of the Zimbabwe-type ruins found here such as Harleigh. The function of these ruins included the control of the people, ie political and administrative functions, thus there must have been surrounding people. The Altar Site has been dated to about 1550 AD and Murahwa's Hill to the Khami Phase, about 1700 AD.

The Inyanga Terraces are of the Portuguese period but are not themselves Portuguese - the typical Portuguese building was rectangular and used timberly (sun-dried) bricks and earth. This phase has within it three major structures:

- . Pits - these, which were not dug into the ground but were built behind a ramp on the slope of a hill, should be called 'pit villages' because of the evidence of numerous surrounding huts and grain bins. Each was probably a family unit with the pit used for small stock - sheep, goats and pigs. The bend in the tunnel is important because sheep and goats remain settled if they cannot see their way out, and today in the Sudan pigs are kept in similar structures.
- . Loop-hole forts - built with large stones in uncoursed, unbattered walls which are reasonably attractive. They are built in defensive positions with the doorways extended into tunnels, huts inside and a raised step (banquette) on the inside of the surrounding wall. In answer to a question Dr. Huffman suggested that the loop-holes were part of the 'gun syndrome' - ie. they were an accepted part of having guns. Even if one did not possess guns they were of certain intimidation value, they could be built later when guns had become available and the weapons themselves were so inaccurate that the narrow field of vision was unimportant.

The records of the Portuguese invasion of 1572 reveal that only the Portuguese had guns (the early Arab traders did not have them) but ten years later the Portuguese lost a major battle because the Africans had acquired guns.

By the mid C17th guns had become the major import, probably because in 1630 the flintlock was invented replacing the serpentine fuse thereby making the weapons more effective and reliable.

A wooden beam removed from one loop-hole fort has been dated to c.1700 AD

- . Terraces - found only in the dolerite areas, they appear to be for the provision of more fertile land, an essential feature in a culture based on shifting cultivation. They

are not continuous suggesting that a small area was terraced at any one time. Also found in association with terraces are grinding hollows used to crush maize, which is a cereal introduced by the Portuguese.

Other associated features include Mahombe Points - small depressions running at right angles into the water courses and probably used to grow root crops - and furrow which are relatively recent (about 200 years ago) and lead water around the hill to the drier areas. Some end in pit villages, others in old agricultural lands.

After 1800 these sites were no longer constructed; the large number of typically Shona refuge-type ruins suggest the invasion of a different culture.

Recently it has been suggested that before the C17th Inyanga was occupied by a Barwe-type people rather than by the Manica. There is linguistic evidence and the pottery is non-Shona; moreover the Barwe, based on Sena, would explain the Portuguese influence.

The Inyanga complex was built in a time of stress caused by a number of wars after 1600 which involved the Monomotapa and which the Portuguese encouraged. It was once this stress was over that the Manica moved into the area.

The main gaps in our knowledge concern that period between the Early Iron Age and the Inyanga culture, and the Umtali area between 1000 and 1500 AD. Dr. Huffman suggests that the History Society could help by choosing an area, say the Mutare River between Fort Hill and the main Inyanga road, because there are pit structures here (surprisingly far south of the Inyanga complex) as well as exhaustive soap stone deposits and holes drilled in surface stone. It also has European historical interest. The area should be walked over thoroughly and all Iron Age sites recorded (preferably in the dry season after ploughing.) Careful excavation of selected sites might fill the gaps in this area.

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The final talk was by Mr. Kuwadza, an inspector in African education, at Marymount. This took the nature of a question and answer session, but some of the points made were:

- . the African is basically a capitalist, wanting more cattle, more children and more wives! It is unlikely that he will become a socialist.
- . the African is keen to please, reluctant to antagonise.
- . conformity is the norm in African society rather than individual success and achievement.

Mr. Kuwadza concluded by saying that he hoped that African customs would survive, that the European would come to understand and respect such customs, and that the African would be able to learn from European civilisation and so develop a unique culture specifically adapted to Rhodesian conditions.

The vitality with which Mr. Kuwadza delivered his talk and controlled the discussion made this one of the outstanding talks delivered to the Society.

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A REPORT ON THE SURVEY AND SURFACE COLLECTION OF A RUIN IN
THE TANDA PURCHASE AREA.

R. Plowes.

Introduction

On March 20th, 1976, a party from the History Society surveyed a ruin in the Tanda Purchase Area. The ruin was on Farm 48 (Map Reference: 1732 C4 Tanda Division VR 310149.) The survey was conducted under the terms of Permit 273 issued on 6.3.76.

The ruin was sited on a granite outcrop in gently sloping open Brachystegia - Acacia grassveld. It had been extensively overgrown. On surrounding hillsides were remains of stone terracing.

Description of Ruin.

The ruin consisted of two major circular walls; an inner and an outer wall. The walls were constructed from granite boulders which had not been dressed. Thus boulders of up to 1 metre in diameter were used and the coursing was irregular.

Both the inner and outer walls had loopholes, many of which had partially collapsed. Each enclosure had only one small tunnel entrance. The outer wall was thicker (up to 2m) and higher (max. ht. 3m.) It also had a banquette running along it at two places.

The tunnel in the outer wall was 1 metre high and had large stone lintels. This tunnel had been narrowed subsequent to building and is presently about 60 cm. wide. A locking device consisted of slots running into the wall inside the tunnel from which stakes could slide across and 'lock' into the adjacent wall. One of the lintels was missing indicating that vertical stakes might also have been used to block the passage. These vertical stakes could have been controlled by someone standing on the banquette.

The outer wall abuts on the inner wall at two places and so probably postdates it. Other evidence for this is that the inner wall has collapsed to a greater extent, and one had loopholes and a tunnel entrance that would become non-functional once the outer wall was constructed.

The inner wall was lower than the outer wall and had no banquettes. The tunnel entrance was similar to that of the outer wall and had a locking device. Inside the tunnel were two pairs of slots for cross stakes. Between the inner and outer walls was a circle of stones, possibly the remains of a grain bin or hut.

Of the twenty odd loopholes only a few were still intact. They generally were square of dimensions 20 x 20 cm. Along the outer wall the loopholes were only a few cms. above the level of the banquette. This would render them non-functional to anyone standing on the banquette, but they could be used by someone standing on the ground.

A small low wall of inferior quality formed a third enclosure on the northern side of the ruin. It abutted on both the inner and outer walls. To the northwest of the ruin in the open veld were many stone mounds and low collapsed walls which could not be interpreted.

Method of Survey.

Two plane table teams and two offset teams worked along a

TANDA PURCHASE AREA
 U.B.H. S. HISTORY SOCIETY, MARCH 1976.
 MAP REFERENCE VR 1932 C4, 310149

Tunnelled entrance with closing device
 Loophole
 F Fireplace
 D Hut daga

Scale 1:200

A B Datum line

datum line shown on the map. The initial maps were drawn to a scale of 1:100. The final map combines the details of the four original maps and thus is fairly accurate.

Finds.

A surface collection made to the east of the outer wall resulted in the following finds:

- Ceramics - a number of undecorated rims, the base of a large jar and one decorated pot sherd.
 Metal - one flattened iron fragment.
 Stone - one dolerite washing stone with cross-marked engravings.
 Daga - The inner enclosure had a hut site, indicated by burnt daga with pole impressions. Near the tunnel in the outer enclosure was a half buried daga structure, possibly a fireplace, surrounded by the remains of a daga wall.

Discussion.

The ruin can be placed in the Inyanga Terrace Tradition. Evidence for this is the irregular coursing, large stones, loopholes, banquettes and tunnels with locking devices. The pottery finds do not dispute this. Although no date can at this stage be attached to the daga remains of huts, there is no direct evidence of any prior or subsequent occupations of the site.

The stone terraces on nearby hillsides are possibly associated with this ruin as they are a feature of the Inyanga Terrace Tradition. Although the small mounds and low walling to the north west of the ruin were probably associated with it, they have no apparent function and cannot be interpreted before further investigation.

The site is not strategically placed from a point of view of defence. Nearby hills would have afforded better protection. However it was built on a source of granite for the walls and relatively near to water. Being in open ground, one has a good view of all approaches.

The loopholes being so narrow and long offer only a narrow range of fire and may have served more as a deterrent; any outsider believing that the occupants possessed firearms. Certainly the loopholes are associated with weapons and thus indicate a Portuguese influence.

Oral tradition, as related by the farm owner, holds the ruin sacred and there is some ritual whereby beerjars are occasionally placed on the walls to satisfy the vadzimu.

Summary.

Evidence suggests that the ruin is of the Inyanga Terrace Tradition and that probably no subsequent occupations are involved. A test excavation should support this hypothesis.

Acknowledgments.

- . Mr. Jan Bekker (Internal Affairs) for locating the ruin and accompanying us on the trip.
- . Mr. I. Bickersteth, D.C. Rusape, for making Mr. Bekker available and for allowing us to use the facilities of the Tanda Rest Camp.

. National Museums and Monuments for loaning us their Land Rover, and to the driver, Mr. Israel Mandapaza.

We appreciate the co-operation of all concerned.

Appendix: other ruins visited in the Tanda T.F.L.

VR 474218 - a dolerite ruin on a hilltop with hut circles and a tunnel entrance. Much terracing and low walling in the adjacent area.

VR 400094 - a well-constructed stock-pit at the base of a granite hill; further walling around the summit with tunnel entrances. A surface collection yielded many decorated pot sherds of the Inyanga Terrace Tradition and one white bead. This site together with the next two were all visible from the road.

VR 394093 - a few granite walls surrounding the summit of a low granite outcrop.

VR 370084 - very similar to the above.

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A Possible Project.

Some ideas extracted from a paper written by Dr. D.N. Beach.

Whereas the political history of the Shona people is being increasingly investigated, the economic aspect is neglected; present papers consist of generalisations which raise more questions than they answer.

What is needed is the microstudy of a single village community; the recreation on paper of an actual village of the late 19th, with an accurate description of its personalities, social relationships, politics, economy and environment.

Requirements: . a village-site readily accessible;
 . a number of elderly people from this village who have accurate memories and a reliable knowledge of traditions.

Method: . single and group interviews;
 . to reduce travel, a sand model of the village and its environment could be used as a visual aid.

Approach: . the major branches of production - hunting, agriculture, gathering, herding, trading - could be investigated in terms of production, distribution and consumption, with particular emphasis on relations of production, ie. the co-operation amongst members of a village.

Then it may be possible to answer such questions as: the extent of game cover in an area; the wild vegetable and fruit resources; the actual number of adults and their "profession"; the effect of tsetse fly; the effects of shongwa (natural disasters such as drought and locusts;) why beads and cloth were valued; the allocation of labour time amongst the sexes; who made pottery, for whom and the reasons for the different styles (important in that it could later be checked by an archaeologist.)

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The Finger Rock Shelter.

On 25th October ten members of the Society together with Mr. Barnes and Miss van Niekerk visited the Finger Rock paintings (VQ 1832 D3 619155) some two kilometres west of St. Augustine's Mission.

The frieze consists primarily of human figures and antelope painted either in a rich red (almost purple) or orange. Nearly all are monochrome although some figures appear in outline only and one large human figure appears to have been shaded in with a series of lateral strokes.

There are in excess of forty human figures, some clearly identifiable as male or female. Most have the pronounced buttocks associated with the Bushmen. There are some fifteen antelope identifiable as kudu, impala or eland. The latter is particularly interesting in that a recent T.V. programme stressed the worship of eland by Bushmen as illustrated by the famous Eland Dance. Other animals could possibly include a warthog, a badger or antbear and some skins pegged out to dry.

One section is unusual in that the fingers of human figures are greatly extended and clearly visible; another shows bows and arrows; another a pattern of dots.

Much is indecipherable but in all cases the 'purple' is superimposed over the orange suggesting that it is more recent. Most of the figures are rather immobile but one or two are exquisite in their sense of movement, sensitivity of line and shape.

All in all a most instructive and fascinating site; we would like to thank Father Prosser of St. Augustine's Mission for permission to visit the site.

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A (Miss)interpretation of Rock Art.

It is on rare occasions that Archaeologists and Anthropologists are able to get a glimpse into the community activities of ancient civilisations. It is with pleasure therefore that I am able to present a brief insight into the family life of those people who gracefully decorated the many cave-shelters of Rhodesia - the Bushmen.

Anthropologists are able to gain valuable evidence from rock art but this has generally been limited to ceremonies and details of hunting - up until now.

On a recent visit to the Finger Rock site, part of the frieze was noted to portray two figures painted in a purple monochrome. The figures were unusual, although readily identifiable as male and female, in that they did not display the typical steatopygia of most other figures in the frieze.

Furthermore, and of great interest, the scene portrays a woman violently beating her spouse (or other male) with a rock or some such weapon. The victim is seen to be crying, symbolically portrayed by long traces of tears. It is possible, alternatively, that the streaks are actually blood streaming from the afflicted wound.

The implications of this scene are profound. Direct evidence of a woman's power in the society is seen. Speculation as to the cause of the punishment is understandable but difficult. There is however reason to believe that parallels in behaviour can be drawn with different civilisations, including our own. Because an archaeologist's work utilizes this technique we can examine the causes of such victimisation in today's society.

Since the revolutionary work of Freud we know that women are emotionally unstable and subject to unpredictable behaviour. Small household incidents such as breaking a tool or failure to express thanks after a meal could easily have led to this medieval tirade.

We therefore must have considerable sympathy for the persecuted painter who sought to immortalize and commit to history the injustice he had suffered. If such events were prevalent in Bushmen society then we must appreciate the burden carried by this prehistoric peasant in his struggle against a domineering spouse.

Certain elements in our society will gleefully observe that the woman had long since burnt her bra.

We have pleasure in contributing this breakthrough in knowledge to the archaeological world. Surely this must rank alongside the work of the late Abbe Breuil who showed 'conclusively' that the South West African Bushmen were ruled by a stranded Phoenician Queen.

For reasons of modesty of this discovery and in order to retain my archaeological credibility, I must remain:

Anonymous.

HISTORY SOCIETY CROSSWORD No. 3.

Last year's crossword was won by R. Bentley of 3A1 and M. Flower of 3A2. Both received free membership of the Rhodesian Prehistory Society.

Once again the Society is offering a worthwhile prize for the winner of this year's competition. Completed entries must be submitted to Mr. Green before the end of February, 1977.

Across

1. Napoleon forced the bridge in Italy. (6)
4. Tests a general meeting, 5th May, 1789. (6)
7. Little Bonaparte takes a sleep. (3)
8. Napoleonic military high schools (6)
9. Aid rag and get a N.African crisis, 1911. (6)
10. Tripoli and Tunis. Altogether a premier sort of name. (3)
11. Bravest of the brave. (3)
12. Three as in Kaiserbund. (4)
13. The origins of George I. (7)
15. Christian name of a popular Bolivian guerilla, d.1967. (3)
16. Law or decree. (3)
18. Lack of government; lawlessness, confusion.
20. Once a part of Fr. Equatorial Africa, independent 1958. (4)
22. A silver strip below a medal as added distinction. (3)
23. 'To get the': literally for Anne Boleyn. (4)
25. Stefan; great Croat leader assassinated in parl. 1928. (6)
26. Boroughs in Eng. which, though virtually uninhabited, still returned 2 M.P.'s to parliament (6)

27. 'Friend' - did this really cause a war? (3)
28. A state in S.E. Europe fills a blank (6)
29. Province of Dreyfus' birth drawn from a scale. (6)

Down.

1. Mdme; leader of Girondins.
2. South or 'Free' France, 1940.
3. I gain sin and an emblem of office. (8)
4. A team of oxen. (4)
5. Stud orientated Eng. sovereigns from Henry VII to Elizabeth I (5)
6. Rabies changes a Balkan state.
12. A low cart without sides. (4)
13. Charles I was irretrievably separated from his, 1649.
14. Br.'s longest reigning monarch. (8)
17. Sacred beetle of the ancient Egyptians. (6)
19. ".... sneezes and Europe catches a cold." (6)
21. Hamid II, Sultan of Turkey, 1896-1909. (5)
22. 1st President of S.A. Rep. (5)
23. Offshoots of Buddhism as practised in S. China. (4)
24. A shortened operation goes up a river. (2)

MARANGE TRIBAL TRUST LAND.

J.Olsen.

(This is an account of a class visit to the Marange TTL as completed by 2A1 in November, 1975. The object was to investigate the reasons for the establishment, and the functions, of a Tribal Trust Land.)

Introduction.

Marange is one of the numerous T.T.L's in Rhodesia; situated in Manicaland it comes under the control of the District Commissioner of Umtali, Mr. F.Taylor. T.T.L's are exclusively for African occupation and no European may own property in them, although there are certain European-based organisations to help African development, eg. Tilcor.

Although many T.T.L's have formed local councils the ruler of the T.T.L. is the chief. Marange, which consists of 520 000 acres and has a population of 85 000, is ruled by chief Hama.

Cattle Sale.

All sales of cattle in the T.T.L's have to be done through the Ministry of Internal Affairs. There are ten dips in Marange and seven sale pens.

On arrival the cattle are sorted into their respective pens and the young and new stock are graded before they enter the auction shed. This grading is done by an expert who uses the following grades:

Cheilla	- superior
GAQ	- good average quality
FAQ	- fair average quality
X	- poor
Reject	- inferior.

The cattle are herded individually into the auction shed where they are weighed in pounds. An Internal Affairs representative converts the weight into kilograms and together with its grade, checks a current price list (which is provided by the C.S.C. and changes every month - it is the minimum or 'floor' price) and relays the price to the auctioneer. The auctioneer calls out the price to the buyers and bidding begins. When the final bid is made a D.A. asks the seller if the price is suitable; if he says no ('Warumba') he reclaims the animal; if he says yes, the animal is branded with the buyer's number and passed into the pens.

1. Seller
2. Cashier
3. Auctioneer
4. Buyers
5. Grader
6. Weigher
7. D.O.
8. Brander

The auctioneer and cashier belong to a company which is contracted to the Ministry of Internal Affairs to control all such cattle sales.

The buyers are private farmers and butchers, and a buyer for the C.S.C. They buy mainly with the purpose of fattening up the cattle in a better environment and re-selling at a higher price. Buyers have to pay a deposit to show their good faith and also a 17½% levy on the price bid for each animal; 10% of this levy goes to the African Development Fund and 7½% to the auctioneer.

On the occasion of our visit very few sales were completed; this was partly because it was early summer and the beasts had not yet gained condition, and partly because some of the sellers had no intention of selling: with school fees due in two months time they wanted some idea of the value of their stock.

Marange Secondary School.

African secondary schools are either F1 (mainly academic study) or F2 (mainly practical) schools. Marange Secondary is a F2 school - as the headmaster, Father Williams said, "It stands for the dignity of manual labour."

The school was founded in 1960 by Bishop Dodge. It is co-ed. and has 358 pupils from grades 8 to 11. Seven subjects are taught: practical agriculture, bricklaying, domestic housecraft, Shona, English, general studies, environmental studies and commerce.

The school has a vegetable garden, pens for ducks and hens, and it's own herd of cattle. The pupils are continually doing projects of some sort; they like group competition but despise individual competition. They have certain boarding rooms where they sleep and cook their own food, looking after themselves. The pupils leave school on Friday afternoon and return on Sunday afternoon or Monday morning. Lessons often run into the afternoon as there is a relaxed atmosphere on time and pupils are given reasonable freedom. Some grades wrote a G.C.E. exam and attained the highest marks in the country.

Teachers are paid 95% of their salary by government and 5% by the local council. At present there are 300 teachers and 10 000 pupils in Marange.

Chieftainship.

The chief's son, Mr. Henry Marange, gave a talk on this subject. The chief of Marange is chief Hama. 'Hama' means friend, which is appropriate because a chief is a friend to his people. Chief Hama, who was appointed in 1961, is 90 years old and blind.

When a chief dies his successor (the eldest son of the relevant family) is chosen at a ceremony organised by the deceased chief's nephew. The zvikiro (medium) goes into a trance and makes contact with the mhondoro (spirit of the founder of the tribe.) He speaks in a foreign tongue which only the elders can understand. During the ceremony the mhondoro will indicate the next chief.

The Ndebele have direct succession from father to son, called

primogeniture succession. The Shona however equate age with wisdom and the chieftainship is shared between a series of houses (collateral succession) thus ensuring that the chief is invariably an old man. To illustrate with a theoretical example:

A, as the eldest son, succeeded his father. During his reign B died, thus on the death of A the chieftainship passes to the eldest surviving brother, C, and so on to E. Thus three houses are established. Note that the progeny of B and D have no further claim to the throne. On the death of E the title will go to the eldest surviving male of A's house, etc.

This is a highly simplified case; the relationships between the houses can get very complicated and disputes as to the succession can rage for years. eg. Three years ago chief Tatazela of the Inyati T.T.L. died and two rival factions laid claim to the title. After many indabas the two factions agreed to let the title go to the chief's son, Mtzhane Kumalo. (Inyati T.T.L. is in Natabeleland.)

When the people meet the chief the traditional greeting is clapping: loud, soft and alternate beats. The chief receives a subsidy from government (about \$120.00 per month.) He is not only the leader and symbol of progress of the people, he is also the chief judge, ie. he maintains discipline and justice within his T.T.L. His jurisdiction today extends only to civil cases - criminal cases are passed on to the B.S.A.P. To help him the chief has a Dare (or advisory council) the members of which are called Magota.

To help him control the T.T.L. the chief appoints headmen (sadunhu) and kraalheads (samusha) who have the same functions as a chief but on a lesser scale.

Agriculture.

A talk by the Agricultural Officer, Mr. Dylton-Hill.

Of the 520 000 acres in Karanga, 217 000 are cultivated, which is about half. Of the 85 000 inhabitants, 17 500 cultivate land; that is, 6 hectares per person. 95% of the cultivated land is a grain crop used only to satisfy the needs of the growers. The remaining 5% is groundnuts, recently introduced as a cash crop.

In a European country about 15% of the population depend on cattle or cultivation for a livelihood; in Karanga this figure is 99,9%, and until farming methods become more intensive this

figure will not decrease. It is too great a load for the land which is suffering from erosion, bad crop management and over-grazing. The job of the Primary Development Officer is to advise and teach the Africans better farming methods; in Marange this is a demanding task; eg. there are 52 000 head of cattle and 60 000 sheep and goats grazing 280 000 acres as opposed to the recommended 360 000 acres. Until cultivation becomes more intensive the grazing area will not increase.

A method of improvement is the 'Master Farmer' scheme. If a farmer completes a three year course on crop rotation, irrigation, insecticides, etc., he becomes a Master Farmer with the right to purchase land in an African Purchase Area. Master Farmer Clubs are formed to help the people of an area introduce proven methods: there are 36 such clubs in Marange together with numerous Young Farmer Clubs.

When the Master Farmer scheme was introduced in Marange, 150 farmers completed the course; today there are 700 such farmers - 3% of the population. A proven example of their ability is their 16 bags per acre of groundnuts as opposed to the $\frac{1}{2}$ a bag average for the T.T.L. Europeans with irrigation and insecticides get 17 bags but admittedly Marange is ideally suited to groundnuts.

The Council.

The Marange Council was formed in November, 1972. Its objective is to supply projects and financial aid for the benefit of the community. Money is collected through rates and fees: every inhabitant over 18 yrs. pays \$2.00 per annum and the Council collects dip fees, dog fees and school fees; it also gets a government grant. Revenue collected up to 30.11.75 was \$72 000, which is used to run 37 schools, 2 clinics operated by a district nurse, and numerous dips.

The structure of the Council is as follows:

President	- District Commissioner	} Executive
Vice-President	- Chief Hama	
Chairman	- Chief's son, Henry	
Councillors	- 7 headmen and 9 elected	
Secretary		} Administrative
Treasurer		
Clerks		

Community Development.

Maranke has a Community Development Training Centre which is used to train Community Advisers. The latter are used to clarify the needs of any particular community and advise them how to attain them; for example, the building of a dam would require the District Commissioner's permission, money, expert advice, labour and transport. If the community itself is willing all of these requirements are available with the co-operation of government and the Council.

Our last visit was to the kraal of Mr. Kafue where Mr. Guier explained to us the layout of a typical kraal and some of the popular customs and traditions of tribal life.

A Tribesman.

When an African is born his name is taken from an event which occurred during his birth.

When one enters a kraal one is greeted according to the time of day (mangwanani; masikati; manheru) and given something to eat (normally groundnuts) to show that one is welcome. When the visitor is greeted the clapping and shaking of hands ensues: males clap with the hands parallel and females with the hands crossed. When shaking, the hand is gripped first around the palm, then around the thumb and again around the palm. If someone has died in the family the palms must then slide off. After this greeting the visitor is taken into the kitchen and, while squatting, is given food.

Huts are made of pole and daga. The floors are a mixture of cow-dung and ant-heap; this combination is long lasting and wards off white ants and insects. The huts are usually built on logs or large stones to keep them off the ground.

The individual does not own land in the T.T.L.; the chief owns all land on behalf of the people and allocates it as he sees fit. This does not encourage permanent improvements by the individual to the land he occupies.

When he dies the tribesman is buried, not cremated. After 12 months a ceremony called Ukubuyisa is held to propitiate the spirit of the deceased. Chiefs in Parange are placed cross-legged in a cave after death.

A tribesman is extremely aware of his mudzimu (plural vadzimu). These are the spirits of his ancestors and they control his destiny; they must therefore be carefully looked after with gifts and good behaviour.

Acknowledgments.

This trip was one of inestimable value; the T.T.L. is a feature unique to Rhodesia and an essential element in understanding the rural African. Understanding between the races is the prime factor for racial harmony in this country.

We are indebted to the following:

Mr. Barnes, for making the trip possible.

Mr. Taylor, D.C. Untali, for coming with us and providing us with so much, both in the material and educational sense.

Mr. Gauer, for so patiently answering our questions.

Father Williams for his hospitality.

Chief Parange and his son Henry, for coming to meet us and for talking to us about the role of the chief.

Mr. Dylton-Hill, for his talk on agriculture.

Miss van Niekerk, for driving the second truck.

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THE PROGRESS AND FUNCTIONS OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN UMTALI.
G.Arthur.

(This was an entry into the junior section of the C.A.H.A. essay competition last year. The section was won by C. Messenger, who has since left us for Prince Edward; this essay was adjudged second. We regret that we are unable to reproduce the many diagrams, pie charts, illustrations and newspaper cuttings that were included in the final project.)

Historical Background.

After managing to occupy the southern, western and northern parts of what was then known as 'the colony', the B.S.A.Co encouraged pioneers and prospectors to occupy and settle what is now Lanicaland. This was in terms of a treaty signed between Colquhoun and Mutasa in September, 1890. Settlement centred around the Bartissol Mining Camp and in May, 1891, after conflict with the Portuguese, a fort was built on top of a steep rise. This could be called the first site of Umtali although there was never any permanent settlement there; the only attraction was the gold claims pegged throughout the valley.

This site was evacuated in December, 1891, and moved to a new situation alongside the Umtali River (the present Old Umtali.)

Rhodes took a great interest in the settlement (he had first seen Rhodesia from the top of the Penhalonga Valley after a strenuous ride up from Beira.) By 1895 Umtali had become a bustling market place and did business with the new trekkers in Melsetter; in fact business was so good that a party was sent to cut a road down to the south to enable the trekkers to bring in their produce with greater ease. Also in 1895 came a telegraph line from Fontes Villa and the beginnings of the railway from Beira. Rhodes had promised that the line would come to Old Umtali; however this proved impossible because of engineering difficulties and Umtali was therefore moved across Christmas Pass to meet the railway.

The Development of Local Government.

In 1892 the citizens of Old Umtali underlined the fact that they wanted some ruling authority in the town; the establishment of a Sanitary Board met their needs but before long it was dealing with all kinds of problems other than that which it stood for. When the town moved to the present site the Sanitary Board continued to meet and practise its authority.

In 1903 a Water Board was established, although it was basically a partnership between the Sanitary Board and the Railways. It was established so that water could be controlled and administered to the town, and both parties shared the profits. This Board continued until the Municipality took over its functions and paid the Railways \$7 000 compensation.

By Government Notice dated 11th June, 1914, Umtali became a Municipality, the third after Salisbury and Bulawayo. The first municipal election was held on 5th August, 1914, and the first municipal council meeting on 12th August.

On 21st December, 1970, the Council decided in the interests of the community to try to raise Umtali to the status of a city; this was duly achieved on 1st October, 1971.

What is Local Government?

The object of local government is to keep a community's local needs maintained and progressing in the right direction. It controls the overall development of the community it represents. This involves building standards, the maintenance of law and order, the provision of water, electricity, sewerage and refuse removal. For the public's safety it provides a fire prevention service, traffic signs and lights; for health it provides an infectious diseases hospital, malaria and bilharzia control and a district nurse. It is responsible for the maintenance of roads, drains, railway sidings, parking bays, bus stops and a bus service; for recreation and culture it provides a swimming pool, library, theatre, the Queen's Hall, African liquor and civic hospitality for important visitors.

Such local government is either an Urban or Rural Council; in Umtali's case it is the latter. At the head of the Urban Council is the Mayor and he presides over all meetings of the Council. His colleagues are his fellow councillors, numbering nine including himself. At the council meetings there are also people to advise the councillors; these are normally the heads of the Municipal departments such as the City Engineer.

The Umtali Municipal area is not large enough to be divided into wards as is the case with Salisbury. The person who co-ordinates the activities of the council and the permanent officials of the Municipality is the Principal Officer.

Most of the work of Council is done by different committees. Each councillor must belong to at least one committee, normally as chairman. For example, both the Mayor and Deputy-Mayor belong to the Co-ordinating Committee which deals with all matters concerning staff or which are of a general nature. The Health and African Administration Committee, the Public Works Committee, the Finance Committee, and Town Lands Committee are the other major committees, and their titles are self-explanatory.

These committees meet before the Council meeting and their decisions are submitted to Council for approval. Any councillor has the right to debate any decision and the result is decided by a majority vote. Council debates are normally short because the ground work has been done in committee earlier.

The decisions of Council are passed on to the heads of the Municipal departments for action by the permanent Municipal employees. The diagram over the page shows the relative positions of government, Council and Municipal employees.

How a Local Government is Formed.

A local government is formed immediately the need arises, which is whenever there is a community's needs to maintain. If it is an urban community the result will be either a city or town council, whereas rural local government deals with small communities such as farmers who want their roads maintained or a village which needs sanitary and water facilities.

URBAN	RURAL
City or Town Council	Rural Council or Village Management Board.
Run by a Mayor & Municipality	Run by a chairman & Committee.

The Council is elected by the community. To qualify for a vote in a municipal election one must first be registered on the National Voters Roll, the qualifications for which are:

People who cannot vote:	under 21 yrs of age	Lunatics or criminals	Cannot speak or read English	Visitors
Europeans can vote when they have:	4 years at Secondary S. and 2 years of earning \$1200 per annum or \$2400 immovable property;		2 years at earning \$1800 p.a. or \$3600 immovable property	
Africans can vote when they have:	2 years at Secondary S. and 2 years of earning \$400 p.a. or \$800 immovable property		2 years earning \$600 p.a. or \$1200 immovable property.	

In Umtali municipal elections are held in August of every year. A councillor is elected for a three year term of office; it is so arranged that of the nine councillors, every year three have to stand for re-election. This ensures continuity on the Council.

A Council Meeting.

Council meets once per month in the Council Chamber (refer diagram.) Its purpose is two-fold:

- (a) to establish bye-laws where necessary, for example the recent Noise and Building Bye-Laws;
- (b) to settle local affairs, for example whether or not to allow the building of an extra butcher's shop in Sakubva. The latest issue concerns the establishment of traffic lights - first whether they are necessary, and secondly if, because of the lack of foreign currency, they can be manufactured in Rhodesia.

The Municipal Departments.

The Treasury: this handles all municipal money, both revenue and expenditure. The main source of income is the rates, which is paid by all persons living in the municipal area, eg. water, electricity and refuse removal as well as vehicle, dog and bicycle licences.

Each job is carefully costed and is submitted to Council for a 'vote' (an allocation of money.) If the vote proves insufficient and more money is required, it has to be re-submitted to Council.

Health Department: is headed by the Medical Officer of Health, Dr. Narraway. It's duties include malaria and bilharzia control (the former is controlled by spraying stagnant pools and the latter by stripping the banks of the streams of vegetation, although bilharzia will continue to be a problem so long

as the streams are used as 'bush P.K.'s';) the removal of refuse to a communal dump; vaccinations and the maintenance of the Infectious Diseases Hospital which, in 1972, admitted 454 European patients. The African I.D. Hospital admitted 1 473 children in 1972 suffering from measles.

Town Clerk's Department: acts as a co-ordinating body between the Council and Municipality, and between the various municipal departments themselves. It handles all the administrative work of the municipality.

African Administration: is situated not in the Civic Centre but in Sakubva. It maintains the Sakubva and Danguavura townships, and has within its structure the same departments as at the Civic Centre: health, roads, buildings, etc.

City Engineer's Department: is divided into four sections:

Water purification takes place up near Lake Alexander after which it is distributed from reservoirs at the top of Christmas Pass to the city. All the sewerage of the city collects in two main sewers which take it to the Sewerage Farm where it is broken down into dried solid matter and virtually pure water. The Works Section maintains public features such as drains, roads, signs and pavements, whilst the Workshops maintains all municipal vehicles and equipment.

Conclusion.

Local Government is not only a beneficial, but obviously an essential, aspect of Untali and its development. Its latest major project has been the new reservoir in Tiger's Kloof to supply the suburb of Greenside. One hopes that it will continue to concentrate on the scenic nature of Untali so that we can justify our claim to be the 'garden city' of Rhodesia.

Bibliography and Sources.

Mayoral Minutes for 1971/72, and ,973/74.

'Government' by R.Howman.

Talks by the Mayor, Mr. D.Reed, and by Mr. C.Slight.

Tours to the Civic Centre and Sewerage Farm.

Attendance at a Council Meeting.

ELIZABETH I.

D. Bentley. 3A1.

(The middle section of the C.A.H.A. Essay Competition was won by R. Papini with his essay on Hannibal. Unfortunately it was nearly 20 000 words in length and would take us in excess of 30 pages to reproduce here. The following essay was awarded the second prize.)

In the first year of his reign, King Henry VIII married his brother's widow, the Spanish princess Catherine of Aragon. By 1518 Catherine had borne him five still-born children, three of them boys. Her only living child at this time was Mary, aged five; Henry was bitterly disappointed. Being only second in the line of Tudors he felt that, to carry on the dynasty he had to produce a male heir. In about 1527 he had caught the eye of one of Catherine's ladies-in-waiting, the vivacious, dark-eyed Anne Boleyn. After Catherine's failures to produce an heir Henry had begun to have doubts as to whether the Old Testament Law, which stated that anyone marrying his brother's widow would be childless, might not be true.

He tried to get the Pope to annul the marriage but, after much deliberation, the Pope refused. Henry therefore put several acts through Parliament, drastically curtailing the Pope's power in England. Even this failed to change the Pope's decision. On January 25th, 1533, Henry married Anne secretly, shortly after proclaiming himself the Supreme Head of the Church in England. The break with Rome was completed when Thomas Cranmer was recognised by the Pope as Archbishop of Canterbury. Almost immediately Cranmer pronounced Henry's marriage to Catherine null and void, so making Mary, now seventeen, illegitimate.

Anne by now was with child and Henry's hasty arrangements to make his forthcoming heir legitimate had succeeded; but he was to be disappointed yet again. On the Sunday afternoon of September 7th, 1533, Elizabeth was born; the first step in her mother's downfall. For the time being however Anne was safe and three days later, to the sound of bells and rejoicing, the baby was christened Elizabeth after Henry's mother, Elizabeth of York.

When three years old Elizabeth was placed in the care of Mary's former governess, Margaret Lady Bryan, and given a separate household based at Hatfield. Elizabeth's household moved between Hunsdon, Chelsea and Greenwich when not at Hatfield, the reason being that any large household staying at one place for any length of time would render it pestiferous.

Elizabeth rarely saw her parents, and when they did visit her the meetings were in the country not in London. On these visits the King saw Elizabeth alone, refusing to see Mary, who by this time had joined Elizabeth's court. Mary regarded Anne as a concubine, and Elizabeth as illegitimate.

Meanwhile at court, Henry had lost his love for Anne and was enamoured with the beautiful Jane Seymour. On showing her resentfulness of this to Henry, Anne was quickly reminded of how easily her position could be lowered to less than it had been before.

Soon after this, in January 1536, Catherine died, so

leaving everything open, once Anne was out of the way, for marriage by Henry to someone else. Almost immediately Anne went into premature labour and miscarried her only hope of remaining on the throne. Following closely upon this extreme disappointment Henry had Anne condemned to death for committing adultery with five men, one her brother. On May 19th she was executed in Tower Green. Henry immediately declared his marriage to Anne illegal so making Elizabeth illegitimate. At this time Elizabeth was having severe teething troubles and so probably did not feel the shock of her mother's death so badly.

Henry married Jane Seymour the day following Anne's execution, and his wish was at last fulfilled when she gave him a son in October, 1537. At the christening both sisters played a part, having been reinstated to favour and soon afterwards re-instated into a joint household, this time as equals. Quite often they were visited by Edward, their brother, and between he and Elizabeth there grew a strong bond of affection.

Jane died in child-birth, so Henry married the unfortunate Anne of Cleves, whom he quickly divorced on account of her ugliness. She was closely followed by Catherine Howard who, unlike her cousin Anne Boleyn, had been quite free with her love before her marriage to Henry. Henry soon found out and had her executed, after which he married Catherine Parr, who was to survive him.

Elizabeth, under the tutorship of Ascham and Grindall, was fluent in Latin and French by the time she was ten, and shortly afterwards in Italian. She was to study Greek until she became Queen. She also studied religion, and she and her sister were accomplished on the lute; Elizabeth furthermore excelled at most sporting pastimes..

Catherine Parr, Elizabeth's last step-mother, did her best to unite the family, giving them a home for the first time and encouraging them in their studies. In 1547 Henry died, but before his death he reinstated Mary and Elizabeth to their rightful succession to the throne. It was with Catherine Parr that Elizabeth lived after her father's death, each admiring the astuteness and intelligence of the other.

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Edward, an unhealthy, pale, nine year old, who had the same fanaticism about Protestantism as Mary had about Catholicism, ruled under the guidance of his uncle, Edward Seymour, who became Protector Somerset.

Seymour's brother Thomas, Lord High Admiral, was jealous of his brother's elevation and determined to marry one of the King's sisters so as to equal his brother's position. He was rebuffed by Elizabeth who told him immediately that she had no intention of ever marrying. Mary was an impossible target because she was a Catholic, so he took the next best course and married Catherine Parr, the late King's widow. Seymour still paid a lot of attention to Elizabeth, who was still living with them, but his wife did not seem to mind. It was only when Catherine found them in each other's arms that Elizabeth left and set up her own household at Cheshunt. Catherine was by this time pregnant and, on Elizabeth's fifteenth birthday, died in childbirth, leaving the way open for Seymour.

Mrs Ashley, Elizabeth's governess, was also very taken with Seymour and so did nothing to curb his attentions to Elizabeth. In Elizabeth's name Mrs. Ashley replied favourably to the Admiral with regard to some of Elizabeth's lands left to her by her father; this was done without Elizabeth's knowledge.

Seymour was indiscreet in his attentions to Elizabeth and his gifts of money had been noted by the Council; on 17th January, 1549, he was sent to the Tower, followed four days later by Thomas Parry, Elizabeth's treasurer, and Mrs. Ashley. Sir Robert Tyrwhitt was sent to Hatfield to extract the truth from Elizabeth. For several days he pitted his wits against hers but all in vain. During this time she wrote several letters to the Protector demanding that she should be allowed to show herself to the people, as rumours had been spread that she was in the Tower, with child by Seymour. Parry had meanwhile told the whole story and with both his and Mrs. Ashley's confessions before her, it was all Elizabeth could do to refuse to admit that either of them had urged her to any practice with Seymour. On March 20th, 1549, Seymour was executed and it caused Elizabeth such a great shock that it was perhaps because of this that she never married.

For the remainder of Edward's reign she applied herself to her studies and carried herself prudently and modestly. She wrote sisterly letters to Edward, congratulating him on his recovery from his latest illness, and in 1551 started visiting Court again. In May, 1553, Edward died, leaving the country in a state of turmoil as to who would be his successor.

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Just before Edward's death, his last Protector, the Duke of Northumberland, married his son to Lady Jane Grey, hoping to place her on the throne instead of Mary. He succeeded in getting Edward to transfer the succession to Lady Jane, and when he died she was proclaimed Queen of England. Northumberland had bribed any opposition to his plan but he had reckoned without Mary, who had the qualities of a Tudor, and when she fled into North Wales all the people rose in her favour. When summoned to London by the new Queen, Elizabeth, supporting Mary, refused, and on the news of Mary's advance, preceded her to London with an army of retainers. Northumberland and Lady Jane fled but were caught and imprisoned, and later executed.

Elizabeth waited for Mary at Wanstead and on July 30th, 1553, they rode into London together. The crowds, although cheering for the new Queen Mary, cheered more at the sight of the graceful Elizabeth who was a constant reminder of the late "King Harry", who was by now remembered with reverence. For a while everything remained peaceful, but it was not long before Mary had Mass celebrated in her own chapel. The meeting of parliament in the autumn was awaited with the knowledge that all Edward's religious acts would be repealed. It was also probable that Mary would repeal Henry's laws and mend the break with the Church of Rome.

It was not long before Elizabeth was told to attend a Mass. To Mary's horror she refused, saying that she could not be expected to attend without instruction due to her Protestant upbringing. She was soon given an instructor and shortly after attended her first Mass, but tried to back out at the last minute by saying that she had stomach pains.

Neither Mary nor her advisers believed Elizabeth and the former showed her displeasure so that the ladies of the Court were afraid to speak to Elizabeth. She therefore set herself out to fascinate the men.

Soon afterwards she was given permission to go to her house at Ashbridge. Whilst there she heard the news of Mary's intended marriage to Philip, heir apparent to the Spanish throne. Her intention was met with great opposition from both her people and Parliament. It led to several risings, the most prominent being that of Sir Thomas Wyatt who intended to replace Mary with Elizabeth and Edward Courtnay (a direct descendant of Edward IV who had been imprisoned during the reign of Henry) on the throne. With great courage Mary won the support of the Londoners by delivering a famous speech in the Guild Hall. The following day Wyatt was refused entry to the town and was soon rounded up and sent to the Tower.

At the first sign of seriousness Mary had sent for Elizabeth, but the latter answered saying she was ill. Mary sent physicians and an escort to collect Elizabeth who came as slowly as possible due to the consequences which awaited her in London. At length she arrived and Mary's advisers immediately set out to interrogate her hoping that she would admit knowledge of the plan. She denied all, even on the production of one of her letters, found in the possession of the French Ambassador, when the examiners tried to make her admit knowledge of foreign support given to Wyatt.

The council was dissatisfied with her answers and determined that she should be taken to the Tower until further evidence could be obtained. On a dismal, rainy Sunday, after a desperate letter to Mary asking for forgiveness and an audience with the Queen which only succeeded in delaying her confinement by one day, she was taken by barge to the Tower. She was taken to a large chamber in which she was housed with a minimum of servants in crude and uncomfortable quarters compared to those with which she was accustomed.

In the Tower she was closely interrogated by Gardiner, Mary's chief adviser, and others; however they could gain no knowledge from her. Wyatt exonerated both Elizabeth and Courtenay on the day of his execution, April 11th, but his words carried little weight and Elizabeth remained in prison. In May however, Philip of Spain was coming to London and it was felt safer to remove her from the capital as there was not enough evidence to have her executed. She was therefore sent to Woodstock under the care of the old but honest Sir Henry Bedingfield. She remained there, despite a letter of protest stating her loyalty, until after Mary's marriage to Philip on July 25th, 1554. In fact it was not until April 30th, 1555, that Elizabeth was summoned to Hampton Court for a lecture by Philip stating that if Mary should die Elizabeth should either marry Philip or accept him as her protege.

She was returned to imprisonment and further attempts were made to extricate the truth from her. When Mary's hopes were dashed (her long awaited pregnancy turned out to be ovarian dropsy) she sent for Elizabeth, and saw her for the first time for a year. In August Philip left her and Mary repaired to Hatfield where the Queen assured her that a fresh rising which had sprung up would not be connected with

her. Philip returned with plans for Elizabeth's marriage to his cousin, Philibert of Savoy. Fortunately for Elizabeth he was unsuccessful and he soon left the country, much to Mary's misery.

Mary and Elizabeth became far more friendly during the summer and each returned the others visits, Elizabeth to Richmond and Mary to Hatfield. On the receipt of a proposition of marriage by Gustavus of Sweden, she immediately referred it to Mary whom she told that she wished to remain unmarried.

Soon afterwards Mary's forces lost Calais, and all that remained after her husband's desertion and her lack of a child was the continuation of the burning of heretics. She died in despair on November 17th, 1558, at daybreak. Elizabeth was walking in the garden when the council brought her the news of Mary's death and she fell on her knees rejoicing on her accession.

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Elizabeth came to the throne of a troubled nation. At her coronation her popularity was shown by the thousands of people who lined the streets as she went by in her gorgeous litter. Every so often she stopped as one of her subjects came up to speak to her, lowering her mode of speech to his level but retaining her unwavering dignity. It pleased her to hear herself compared to Henry, but in no way was she going to make the same mistakes that her father had made: of joining a European quarrel and then being tricked by the power he supported. Neither was she going to commit the folly that both Mary and Edward had made; of forcing people to worship in one specific sect.

A tall graceful figure, accomplished at most sports and with a love for dancing, she had a brilliant intellect and a knack for choosing the right people for the right positions. She came to the throne of a small power which had to align itself with France or Spain or itself be wiped out. Within the country there was incessant strife between the Catholic and Protestant causes. Instead of immediately reverting to the Protestant cause, Elizabeth gently changed the policy of the government from Catholic to a position which pleased both sides without giving either an obvious advantage.

The loss of Calais had caused great anger in England but as Elizabeth could not afford another war she had to retain the peace but in such a way as not to bring shame on her country's name. By allowing France to keep Calais but to pay large sums of money to England she gained a useful ally and prevented a war.

On her accession she immediately chose Sir William Cecil as her principal secretary. Between them there was a great trust which was to be an important factor for forty years, he as her chief adviser and councillor, probably knowing her better than anyone else, and she as his Queen. His extreme interest in affairs of the realm and his cautious good judgement were often her only anchor; in him she had a man on whom she could rely. Around her she placed in important positions the most able Protestant minds: Nicholas Bacon she appointed her Lord Keeper of the Great Seal; Mathew Parker was her Archbishop of Canterbury, and Roger Ascham, a famous scholar and her former tutor, was permanently by her side.

Philip of Spain, through his Ambassador, sent presents of jewels to Elizabeth, who accepted them gratefully. It was not unreasonable to suspect that Elizabeth would want to marry him, thereby strengthening her position in the eyes of the Catholics who had hoped for a Catholic Queen, the obvious choice being Mary Queen of Scots. Although her husband was only heir apparent to the French throne, Mary had no uncertain claim to the English crown. Elizabeth, knowing this, helped Scottish Protestants openly and, to the horror of Europe, invaded Scotland. By the treaty of Edinburgh, Henry of France, having no resources, was forced to withdraw all his troops except for a select few. Mary's husband soon became Francis II but shortly afterwards died leaving Mary, his widow, to return to Scotland. So began their long duel, Mary to gain the English throne, Elizabeth to keep it.

Meanwhile Elizabeth's advisers were trying to get her to marry. She refused to become a Catholic and marry Philip, saying that she was a heretic, so he promptly tried to marry a French princess, which Elizabeth found most disconcerting. However she promised her council that she would never marry a foreigner and that she would marry only for the good of the country. Realising her political value for marriage she encouraged suiters only to find some excuse at the last moment to prevent marriage. At times the rumour was rife that she was unable to bear children, especially so between 1559 and 1561; several physicians however are reported to have stated that she was physically capable of having children.

During her reign, and after a friendly childhood together, Lord Robert Dudley, youngest son of the last Lord Protector, won her favour. He remained her favourite until his death and, had she not been Queen, Elizabeth might have married him after the tragic death of his wife. Talk was abroad that she was his mistress and Elizabeth eventually had to send him away from Windsor to avoid further scandal.

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After Mary's return to Scotland she and Elizabeth had tried to be friends, sending amicable letters to one another, although it is unlikely that they could ever have succeeded. Mary offered a constant threat to Elizabeth's security, while Elizabeth represented a permanent obstacle to Mary's ambitions. They planned a meeting to get to know each other better but it was postponed due to Elizabeth's support of the Protestant Huguenots in a French civil war. Mary was the second best match in Europe and Philip of Spain directed his attentions towards her on behalf of his son and heir. This was intolerable to Elizabeth who offered Mary the choice: war if she married a Catholic or peace if she married a Protestant, namely Robert Dudley, recently created Earl of Leicester to make him acceptable to Mary. Mary would have accepted Leicester had she been a guaranteed heir to the throne because of it, but Elizabeth refused. Mary, in anger, married the degenerate Lord Darnley, another descendent of Henry VIII, a marriage which she was to regret.

Darnley was vicious and unlikeable after their marriage and she turned in desperation to her friend Rizzio whom she made her secretary. He was murdered shortly afterwards on Darnley's orders and in front of Mary. Following this episode Mary gave birth to the probable heir of both England and

Scotland; Elizabeth, as Godmother, sent a gold font for his christening. But the peace was short-lived: Darnley stood in the way of Mary's new goal, the Earl of Bothwell, with whom she had fallen madly in love. Bothwell engineered Darnley's murder in an explosion and married Mary.

The murder shocked Scotland and Mary soon found Bothwell a bully and a tormentor. Opposing factions took advantage of the position and started a revolt which forced Mary to flee to England and so to Elizabeth's mercy. Elizabeth imprisoned her for Darnley's murder as she did not wish Mary to leave England, and established a Court of Inquiry to look into the matter. Scottish Lords were summoned to York where they produced conclusive evidence that Mary was a murderess. There were however rumours that the letters produced as evidence were forgeries; in the meantime Mary was kept prisoner.

Mary in England was a constant threat to Elizabeth and it was not long before, with the promise of help from Spain, the Earls of Westmoreland and Northumberland attempted to release her. She was immediately removed to Coventry and the conspirators caught and hanged. This included some 700 peasants of the north who were hanged by martial law on village greens.

Early in 1570 the Pope issued a Bull excommunicating Elizabeth thereby giving the Catholics a choice between loyalty and treason. Mary's marriage was declared invalid and Norfolk declared himself a Catholic and prepared to marry her. His intentions discovered, he was tried and, despite Elizabeth's hesitation, was executed for high treason. The northern failure to stage a revolt had broken the power of the old nobility once and for all; the monarchy was at last supreme.

In France, after a political alliance signed at Blois in April, 1572, the ruling house of Guise suddenly caused a massacre of the Huguenots. Elizabeth wore black to show her displeasure but still remained as Godmother to the French king's baby and continued marriage negotiations with his brother. Meanwhile the Netherland Protestants were trying to free themselves from the Spanish yoke. Elizabeth sent money and promised men who never arrived, but when the Dutch received their independence Elizabeth refused to recognise it as a breach with Spain would have been extremely embarrassing at that time.

During the 1570's there was an influx of Catholic conspirators into England and various attempts were made on Elizabeth's life. Several people were executed for high treason but in the last thirty years of her reign Elizabeth executed only 300 people for treason - the same number that Mary had burnt in the last three years of her reign.

To ensure a Protestant heir to the English throne the Queen's latest adviser, Walsingham, wanted Mary's death and he plied Elizabeth with evidence of Mary's involvement in plans for Elizabeth's murder. In 1585 a conspiracy by Anthony Babington was uncovered and Mary's connivance was undeniable. The case was put before the Council; Elizabeth was persuaded that Mary's death was a political necessity, and she was tried and found guilty of high treason.

On February 8th, 1587, despite a last attempt by Elizabeth

to save her, Mary was executed at Fotheringay Castle. Bonfires were lit and there were celebrations all over England, but Elizabeth wept in her apartments, mourning more the execution of a Queen than a woman. Elizabeth, without any trouble, shifted the responsibility from her shoulders onto those of her advisers. Cecil bore the brunt of her hysteria which lasted for several weeks. Elizabeth never forgave herself for allowing Mary's execution to take place.

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After Mary's execution further rebellion was useless as even if it did succeed there would be no one to replace Elizabeth on the throne. This was the main factor which helped to keep those formerly violently opposed to Elizabeth quiet and even loyal during the great crisis which was to descend on England.

Outside England the matter was regarded differently. In Paris popular indignation was intense, the execution being regarded as an insult to the French nation and requiring vengeance. However war was averted as Henry of France was faced with a position in which Elizabeth was negotiating for peace with Philip of the Netherlands and Henry could not possibly undertake a war against the combined might of England and Spain.

In Spain Philip II used the peace negotiations as a convenient blind until he was ready to pour the whole might of that nation into an attempt to crush England for ever, so, as he thought, safe-guarding his Empire. Sparked off by English 'pirates' capturing Spanish treasure ships returning from the West Indies with the gold which kept the Spanish economy alive, Philip was given an excellent excuse in Mary's execution.

Philip had traced his descent from John of Gaunt and with Mary's death he put forward his own claim to the throne. Once England was in his power he planned to place one of his daughters on the throne to rule in the name of Spain. He thus set about building his acclaimed 'Invincible Armada' with the monetary aid of his Italian bankers and the sceptical Pope Sixtus V who felt obliged to support the Catholic faction.

Meanwhile in England John Hawkins had been replacing the old style of ships with a new, faster vessel which could easily out-manoeuvre the clumsy Spanish galleons. With the threat of Spain so imminent the Queen eventually sanctioned an expedition by Drake to prevent Spanish and foreign ships from joining up with the main Armada. Drake was also ordered to prevent the ships from getting victuals, to prevent any progress towards England and to cut off any ships from the West or East Indies. At the last moment Elizabeth, cautious to the end, ordered the expedition not to set out.

The message never reached Drake who conveniently set sail early and immediately went into action against the Spaniards. He forced his way into Cadiz harbour despite heavy Spanish land armament and succeeded in burning a large number of Spanish ships and destroying their accumulated stores and ammunition. He went on to capture Cape St. Vincent and blockaded Lisbon harbour for four weeks before returning home, on the way capturing a Portuguese carrack worth £114 000,

which turned out to be three-quarters of the defence costs against the Armada. Officially disavowing his actions, the Queen cheerfully accepted £40 000 for her own profit. Drake's valient and courageous action, commonly known as 'The Singeing of the King of Spain's Beard', successfully prevented the despatching of the Armada against England for a full year.

During this time Elizabeth prepared the country against invasion with the help of her able advisers. She appointed Lord Howard of Effingham Lord Admiral and Drake Vice Admiral, but in neither did she endow her complete trust, retaining for herself the task of issuing the fleet with the finance necessary for its equipping and victualling. The Queen has unjustly been accused of parsimony regarding the victualling arrangements but the strain of equipping such a vast fleet together with that of fitting out the large army required to defend the country on land put a severe strain on the country's finances. It was only Elizabeth's diplomacy that saved England from near bankruptcy. Neither can Elizabeth be blamed for the lack of powder; no one could have foreseen the vast amount of gun powder that was to be consumed during the nine days fighting in the channel. Elizabeth's demanding to know the proportion of powder and shot required by the Admiral shows the beginnings of a really efficient civil service. In fact the English fleet was far more adequately supplied than the Spanish.

Under the command of the Earl of Leicester, who was seconded by an experienced soldier, Sir Roger Williams, an army of 20 000 men was assembled at Tilbury to repel the invaders should the navy fail to do so. To intercept the Armada at sea the main fleet was stationed at Plymouth under the command of Howard of Effingham. Sir Thomas Howard with a smaller fleet watched the Straits of Dover should the enemy slip past the Admiral.

After Drake's invasion of Cadiz Philip set about preparing his fleet for an invasion of England during the following year. On the death of his Admiral and best sailor, Santa Cruz, Philip appointed the Duke of Medina Sedonia as supreme commander of the Armada. As the latter was not a good sailor, and felt that he was not up to the task, and already had misgivings about the Armada, the whole enterprise was beginning to give premonitions of failure.

The Spanish fleet, imposing but altogether an unwieldy array of vessels, was made up of merely 50 men-of-war out of 130 ships. Containing 50 000 soldiers it was equipped more for a battle on land than on sea. Had the invasion fleet been self-contained it might have had some chance of success, but as it had to join up with a large section of the force, sent from the Netherlands by the Duke of Parma, it was already hindered. The English fleet rendered the merging of the Spanish and Dutch fleets impossible and there was no choice for Medina Sedona but to invade England alone.

When the Spanish fleet eventually set out in May, 1588, its dispersals by the winds forced it to return and reform in Spain. It was not until July 19th that it was sighted at the mouth of the Channel. It was probably on this day that Drake, due to unfavourable winds, was confined to Plymouth harbour and played his legendary game of bowls.

Drake led the English fleet out of Plymouth to meet the Armada, which must have been an impressive sight: 130 ships spread out across the Channel in arrow-head formation. He intended to meet it in a running battle so keeping it off the English coast. In this he succeeded, the battle running for a week, making progress at only one mile per hour due to adverse head winds. Taking advantage of the superior speed, qualities and gun powder of the English fleet Drake succeeded, in his own words, "to pluck their feathers."

Desperate Medina Sedonia sought shelter in the safety of the Calais roads. Drake, undaunted, sent fire ships in to oust them from their apparently safe anchorage. Lord Howard took over, mustering the whole of the English force to stage an all out attack at dawn to drive the Armada aground on the treacherous Flemish banks. After an eight hour battle, during the night of the 28th several Spanish ships ran aground and by the 29th all that remained for the Armada to do was to flee round the coasts of Ireland and Scotland. However a great storm arose and drove it through mountainous seas onto the treacherous coast or merely sank the ships without trace. Few vessels of that mighty Armada returned to tell their tale of woe and disaster to their furious king.

England's navy had saved her from one of the greatest threats she was ever to know. Throughout the time that invasion was imminent Elizabeth carried herself with the regal courage and dignity befitting such a great prince during such perilous danger. This is fully evident in her speech at Tilbury, made after reviewing the troops summoned to defend the nation:

"My loving people, we have been persuaded by some that are careful of our safety, to take heed how we commit ourselves to armed multitudes, for fear of treachery; but I assure you, I do not desire to live to distrust my faithful and loving people. Let tyrants fear; I have always so behaved myself that, under God, I have placed my chief strength and safeguard in the loyal hearts and good will of my subjects. And therefore I am come amongst you at this time, not for my recreation and sport, but being resolved, in the midst and heat of the battle, to live or die amongst you all, to lay down, for my God, and for my Kingdom, and for my people, my honour and my blood, even in the dust. I know I have but the body of a weak and feeble woman, but I have the heart of a King, and of a King of England too; and think foul scorn that Parma or Spain, or any Prince of Europe, should dare to invade the borders of my realms; to which, rather than any dishonour grow by me, I myself will take up arms; I myself will be your general, judge and rewarder of everyone of your virtues in the field. I know already, by your forwardness, and that you have deserved rewards and crowns; and we do assure you, on the word of a Prince, they shall be duly paid to you. In the mean my Lieutenant General shall be my stead, than whom never Prince commanded a more noble and worthy subject; not doubting by your obedience to my General, by your concord in the camp, and by your valour in the field, we shall shortly have a famous victory over the enemies of my God, of my Kingdom and of my people."

The inscription of one of the medals struck to commemorate the victory, described the faith of Elizabeth and her sailors:

'Flavit Deus et Dissipati Sunt' - God blew and they were scattered. Poets, couriers and the whole nation paid homage to their sovereign who, to them, represented the vanquishing of the great Armada. The victory against Spain had been decisive and England had emerged as a great power.

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The years following the Armada were the greatest of Elizabeth's reign, although perhaps not the happiest for her. Only a month after the Armada victory Leicester died and for weeks the Queen was completely absorbed with her grief, only pausing from her self-imposed solitary confinement to visit his grave. The passing of Leicester aged her considerably and the beginnings of old age began to show. Although only fifty five she was older than any of the preceding Tudors at the time of their deaths. Worry began to show as the men on whom she depended died one by one. In 1590 Walsingham died, followed by her second favourite and Lord Chancellor, Hatton. After a long illness even her arch rival, Philip died, leaving her the senior European monarch. Her great friend and adviser, Burleigh, was not to die until 1598.

New favourites, however, appeared: the famous Raleigh and Hatton, son of the late Lord Chancellor, kept Elizabeth's youth alive with their attentions. It was Robert Devereux, Earl of Essex, who captured her favour in the last years of her life. The step-son of Leicester, it was men like he who tore the Court in half with strife between supporting factions.

Elizabeth's foreign policy remained the same, prudent and cautious. She could not hope for peace after the Armada and supported anyone who opposed Spain. She sent help to the Dutch and supported Henry of Navarre against the Catholics who still opposed his accession to the French throne.

Internal tranquility was threatened by that extreme Protestant sect, the Puritans, who wished to see major reforms within the English church. Also unhappy were the merchants, formerly Elizabeth's mainstay, who detested the monopoly set up by courtiers or other favourites who granted privileges only to a select few. One age was gradually dissolving into another, and only Elizabeth herself seemed to resist this change, although she was still full of vigour with as much wit as ever; she could still dance the night through after hunting all day. She was still as popular as ever, if not more so, as increasingly she regarded herself as the mother of her people.

Essex and others however felt that she was being used by the Cecils for their benefit and wished to destroy them. Essex, as leader of the opposition, was unlike her other favourites in that he was extremely popular with the people. An extremely handsome, clever man, with a love for music and the arts, he was an excellent soldier. But above all he was an open, liberal man with the qualities of honour and truthfulness rare in any subject. It was this that endeared him to his Queen and followers.

The Queen paid much attention to him, thus causing scandalous gossip to run abroad due to jealousy and misunderstanding. Elizabeth could not resist the temptation to make men as able in their writings as Raleigh, Sidney and Essex compete to tell her how beautiful and gracious she was. She never fully

forgave Essex for marrying the daughter of Sir Francis Walsingham, refusing to receive his wife at court. She forgave him sufficiently to lead an expedition, together with Howard and Raleigh, to sack Cadiz in the summer of 1596. It was highly successful but the prize was not nearly as great as Elizabeth had hoped. This expedition brought on another Armada from Spain, but this was scattered by the weather and returned to Spain a failure.

The expedition to Cadiz together with the welcome he received from the people was a magnificent success for Essex. His popularity was enhanced by the chivalrous forbearance with which he treated the inhabitants of Cadiz. His success soon led him to ruin however. He was given command of the greatest force and was given the widest powers ever entrusted to an English commander in Ireland. He was a dismal failure. Miserably out-manoeuvred by the enemy, he arranged an armistice which was bitterly condemned by Elizabeth. He was recalled and shortly afterwards arrested. Only due to a sudden illness and disuasion by Elizabeth's advisers did Essex retain his offices and was he allowed to return to his house still nominally under arrest. Two months later he was permitted to be released but forbidden to go to Court and was refused the return of his main source of income - a monopoly in sweet wines. This treatment enraged Essex and on 9th February, 1601, he attempted to raise the people of London and take Whitehall. The news leaked out, Whitehall was barricaded and Essex had a cold reception from the people; he was forced to surrender and was sentenced to death. He was executed - and this time the Queen signed the death warrant without hesitation and accepted full responsibility for this action.

At the end of October, 1601, she summoned her last parliament. It was troubled by the number of patents lately issued by Elizabeth. The uproar in the House won a stinging rebuke from Mr. Secretary Cecil but Elizabeth, preferring more subtle methods, abolished several monopolies forwith.

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Elizabeth showed the great love she bore her people and her country when she received a deputation from Whitehall on 30th November, 1601, with these words:

"Though God has raised me high, yet this I count the glory of my crown that I have reigned with your loves. I do not so much rejoice that God hath made me to be a Queen as to be a Queen over so thankful people."

In the simplest words she expressed the guiding motive of her existence:

"I have cause to wish nothing more than to content the subject; and that is a duty which I owe. It is my desire to live nor reign no longer than my life and reign shall be for your good."

Harrington's words: "We loved her, for she said she did love us", show their mutual affection for one another.

Ill from a cold already, an extreme illness was brought on by her great friend the Countess of Nottingham's death. She died on March 24th, 1603, at 3 o'clock in the morning, the Archbishop of Canterbury praying by her bedside to the end;

"My little black husband," as she once called him. She was succeeded by her Godson, James VI of Scotland, now James I of England.

References:

Sir John Neale	Elizabeth
Elizabeth Jenkins	Queen Elizabeth
Mona Wilson	" "
Milton Waldman	" "
G.W. Woodward	" "
E.A. Murphy	The Girlhood of Queen Elizabeth.
Sir L. Strachey	Elizabeth and Essex.
A.L. Rowse	The England of Elizabeth
Sir. W. Churchill	A History of the English Speaking People
" "	Heroes of History
" "	The Island Race
R.J. Unstead	Struggle for Power
S.T. Bindhoff	Tudor England
L. du G. Peach	Sir Walter Raleigh
Readers' Digest	All the World's a Stage

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The Murder of Marat.

T. Harrold, 3A1.

Jean Paul Marat called himself a martyr of liberty. But he was an avowed killer in a city of death ... until Charlotte Corday decided to intervene.

For many days 25 year old Charlotte Corday had thought deeply about the plight of the French and the fate of her fellow citizens. Since the storming of the Bastille and the flight of Louis XVI the country had been ruled by the leaders of the French Revolution.

She had once been a fervent revolutionary, but now she felt that the new regime had gone too far in its atrocities. One aristocratic family after another had gone to the guillotine and finally, on 21st January, the King himself was executed. This plus the proposed execution of Marie Antoinette, was too much for Charlotte. The man she blamed most for the increasing bloodshed was Marat, a doctor-turned-politician and leading member of the extremist Jacobin party.

Marat was noted for goading the Paris mobs into frenzied bursts of vengeance and hatred. He had been arrested several times for his revolutionary actions; he would not be content, he vowed, until every high-born Frenchman was lying headless in an unmarked grave.

By the beginning of July, 1793, Charlotte had convinced herself that Marat should die. "As long as he lives there will be no more safety for laws and humanity," she once said. She told her father that she was going to do a favour for a friend and, with murder in her heart, she left Caen.

Charlotte's decision to assassinate Marat was not an impulse of over-emotion of a young girl. She was a member of the Girondin Republican Party which had opposed Louis' death and had tried to rescue him from the guillotine, and now she had developed a hatred of Marat which extended to his grotesque physical features.

The plot weighed on Charlotte's mind as the coach took her from Caen to Paris. She arrived on Friday, 12th July, and booked in at a quiet hotel. Early the next morning she went to an iron-monger's and bought a kitchen knife which she hid in her dress. Then after breakfast she made her way to Marat's house where his maid explained that it would be impossible to disturb Marat as he spent most of his time each Saturday soaking in a medical bath in an effort to cleanse his skin of a disease which he had contracted whilst hiding in the Paris sewers from his political opponents.

Undeterred Charlotte returned to her hotel and and composed a letter:

'Citizen, I have just arrived in Paris from Caen. Your love for your country makes me certain you will want to hear of the unfortunate events that are happening in that part of the Republic. Be kind enough therefore to grant me a moment's interview. I will put you in a way of rendering a service to France.

Charlotte Corday.'

After Marat had read the note she was sent directly to him, and was shown straight to the bathroom. She was struck by the lack of furniture, the bare brick floor, the map of France on the wall and a brace of pistols with the word 'death' scrawled above them. Marat stared at her through the steam:

"Well, what is this news that makes you so determined to see me?" Charlotte hesitated and then drew near the bath:

"The deputies in Caen are planning to form a corps for the federal army; they mean to march on Paris and overthrow the Jacobins."

Marat reached for his quill and paper. "Come then," he said, "give me their names." With her brain racing Charlotte quickly recited a list which she had made up. As she came to a halt the quill stopped scratching and Marat nodded grimly:

"Excellent. I shall have them brought here immediately. They shall be guillotined within a week."

This was the moment. With one rapid movement she plucked the knife from her breast and plunged the blade into Marat's bare chest. "Help, my friends," he cried, "Help, I'm being murdered."

But it was too late; when help arrived Marat was on the verge of death. Charlotte was arrested and when asked why she had done it replied "Due to Marat civil war was about to break out all over France. In killing him, and sacrificing my own life, I am preventing the downfall of France."

She was taken to prison to await trial. On 16th July, 1793, she was sentenced. She had become impatient and interrupted the witnesses by shouting "These details are a waste of time. I killed Marat - sentence me now."

She was found guilty and sentenced to death. She was taken through the Paris streets in a tumbril ... to become another of the many victims of Madame La Guillotine.

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The Malayan and Rhodesian Terrorist Wars - A Comparison.

J.Olsen 3A1.

To understand the types of war fought some background of each country is required:

1. Race

Malaya - the Malayan terrorists came from the Chinese group, a minority in a cosmopolitan country.

Rhodesia - the Rhodesian terrorists come from the major racial group - African - although there are strong tribal differences.

2. Geographical.

Malaya - 50 000 sq. miles, 4/5th jungle. Sub-divided into distinct states under the rule of Sultans.

Rhodesia - 150 000 sq. miles, mainly open savanna. Sub-divided into white areas, TTL's and merger areas of African and European. TTL's under tribal chiefs.

3. Political.

Malaya - British colony, therefore received Commonwealth and imperial support. Terrorists had one political party, the M.C.P.

Rhodesia - Ex-British colony (declared UDI 11.11.65) therefore she has received no foreign aid. Many terrorist political parties - Zanu, Zapu, ANC, Third Force, Zipa.

These terrorists came/come from the ranks of the political extremists. Others in their race or party may differ completely in attitude, eg. the terrorists as opposed to the R.A.R. of the Security Forces. It is therefore a war of ideology, not of race.

Use and Structure of Security Force Manpower.

Malaya was a British colony and therefore received unlimited manpower and support from Britain and the Commonwealth, whilst Rhodesia is an independent state. The strategic objective of the terrorist/guerilla is to tie-up as many troops into terrain which renders conventional warfare impossible. Rhodesia uses an imaginative, flexible, mobile, small army; this type of warfare has proved successful in the Congo by Mike Hoare's 'Flying Columns' and by the 'Green Berets' in Vietnam. These highly mobile forces combined with protected villages are the high points in containing terrorist insurgency. The military conservatism in Malaya based on large numbers of troops as in European warfare failed in Mocambique (army of 60 000) and Angola; also in Indo-China, Algeria and Vietnam. These failures have been a blind adaptation of European warfare in a theatre least suitable for it.

Britain used colonial troops who did not have a personal stake in Malaya. Rhodesia has native troops (black and white) fighting for their own country.

In overall command in Malaya was a Supremo - Gen. Templer. He had direct control over the war. Under him was the Rhodesian equivalent of J.O.C. - the District War Executive Committee. Templer co-ordinated all branches of the Security forces preventing inter-service and departmental rivalry and thus lack of liaison, co-ordinating the intelligence departments and the forces taking the resultant action. The overall result was the rapid direction of policy to all Services.

The Structure of Terrorist Manpower.

. In Malaya terrorist forces were united under the M.C.P. both politically and militarily with Chin Peng as head. Rhodesian terrorists are disunited in both spheres.

. Both were terrorist forces, not, as sometimes claimed in Rhodesia's case, guerillas. A guerilla attacks the enemy security forces by a war of attrition, both physical and psychological, based on breaking their control of an area by attacking supply routes, lines of communication, etc. The terrorist bases his campaign on the civilian population in which by intimidation he seeks to undermine the government's control and authority in that area. A terrorist is a criminal and, as in Malaya, if proved guilty is hung (see appendix 1.) The Malayan Chinese Terrorist (C.T.) was a guerilla under the British Force 136 during the war, 1942-45.

. The C.T.'s were war veterans, trained in Special Training School 101 under Lt.Col J.Gavin, Singapore. They formed the Malayan Peoples Anti-Japanese Army which in 1948 became the Malayan Peoples Anti-British Army (M.P.A.B.A.) The Rhodesian terrorist is, on the whole, poorly trained and experienced.

Policies and Tactics of Security Forces.

. Use of helicopter borne warfare in both countries differed widely. Rhodesian S.F.'s base their entire counter-insurgency (COIN) operations on the helicopter while British troops used it in a limited support role. The different use of the helicopter lies in the different terrain. Larger areas can be covered by one helicopter than by a number of troops on the ground. After an incident troops can be moved swiftly to the area despite any rugged terrain which would tie up ground troops. This weapon is vital to Rhodesian S.F.'s due to their limited manpower.

. Protected villages were first formed in Malaya in 1951 of which the main occupants were Chinese squatters. Implemented in Rhodesia at the beginning of operation Hurricane in the N.E., they won the support of the people by protecting them from terrorist intimidation. They also:

- . give the S.F.'s more control over population movement;
- . give the S.F.'s easier administration of the people;
- . isolate terrorists from food supplies thereby causing them to attack the S.F.'s on their own ground unlike usual insurgent procedures;
- . force the terrorist to move inside a vacuum without being able to hide in the population. This destroys Mao's own dictum 'People are to guerillas as water is to fish';
- . cause in the long term an economic growth point.

. Both S.F.'s realised the value of obtaining the support of the people. "The answer lies not in pouring more troops into the jungle but in the hearts and minds of the people." Gen. Templer, Malaya, 1952.

. Both governments offered rewards leading to the death or capture of a terrorist. Malaya offered \$4000; Rhodesia offers \$1000. At 1948 sterling prices these sums are identical. This weapon caused grave concern amongst terrorist leaders resulting in a lack of trust and therefore in weaker operations.

. Malayan S.F.'s rehabilitated surrendered C.T's with good results and were used against their ex-comrades in both physical and propaganda campaigns. This is not done officially in Rhodesia.

. Malayan S.F.'s carried out concentrated efforts in different provinces to wipe out the terrorist cancer in a 'contain and hold' campaign. As soon as one province was clear of terrorists it was declared a 'White Area' and troops were moved out and concentrated elsewhere. This is not managed in Rhodesia.

. Due to terrorist tactics Rhodesia has had to adopt measures to contain terrorist incursions, eg. Hot Pursuit, which is a very delicate and difficult weapon to employ. (See Appendix 2.)

Policies and Tactics of the Terrorist

. Both groups of terrorists fight/fought a Mao Tse-tung type of warfare, ie take control of the countryside and isolate the cities which will then fall. In Malaya the terrorists were supplied from China; Rhodesian terrorists are supplied indirectly from the U.S.S.R. and China.

. The first unified incursion of terrorists into Rhodesia was on August 28th, 1967, into Matabeleland between the Victoria Falls and Kazungula. Their objectives were to establish camps inside Rhodesia, lay arms caches and train the locals in basic insurgency tactics. This was repeated in the Zambezi Valley incursions from December 27th, 1967. The C.T's in Malaya operated from existing camps of Force 136, asserting their control over the local population surrounding their camp. At this stage terrorist tactics in each country were similar. Then by a windfall African nationalists gained a secure base south of the Zambezi in 1974 - Mocambique. From Mocambique terrorists could operate 'hit and run' tactics with no need to remain in dangerous country. This resulted in Rhodesian S.F.'s having to adopt different tactics to their Malayan counterparts, ie. Hot Pursuit.

. Both terrorist groups tried to assert their control over the local population by brutal intimidation.

Conclusion.

During both terrorist campaigns the Governments declared a State of Emergency - a State of War might have been too drastic a step but furthermore in a State of War the terrorist is recognised as a lawful belligerent. (see Appendix 1). Also in Malaya's case insurance on the rubber and tin was covered in a State of Emergency but not in a State of War.

The C.T's used as a political cover - in order to make Malaya a Chinese satellite - that they wished to free Malaya from British Imperialism and make her independent. Then Whitehall granted Malaya independence (31st August, 1957) destroying the C.T's political base. The C.T's refused to accept this independence.

When Malaya became independent the M.C.P. was recognised as a lawful party and allowed to participate in elections. But Malaya has not turned communist; when people are shown Communism in its true undisguised form they reject it.

The extreme African nationalists used as an argument that they fight for majority rule. Now that majority rule has been assured they reject it, their facade destroyed. The support they had gained from the free world now seems rather dubious. And on principle the Western world cannot deny a struggling African nation arms for fighting Soviet Imperialism. This fully reveals that there are communists: our borders, not nationalists fighting to establish a democratic state. Rhodesia will become an extension of the Cold War.

Appendices.

1. The Red Cross Convention of 1949.

Article 4.

"A. Prisoners of war, in the sense of the present Convention, are persons belonging to one of the following categories, who have fallen into the power of the enemy:

- 2) ... including such organised resistance movements for fulfilling the following conditions:
 - a) that of being commanded by a person responsible for his subordinates;
 - b) that of having a fixed distinctive sign recognisable at a distance;
 - c) that of carrying arms openly;
 - d) that of conducting their operations in accordance with the laws and customs of war."

ie. terrorists do not qualify for P.O.W. status.

2. The Munroe Doctrine.

The relevant part of the Munroe Doctrine is the amendment of Aug. 2nd 1912 by the then Senator H.Cabot Lodge which declared that ... when any harbour or other place in the American continents is so situated that the occupation thereof for naval or military purposes might threaten the communications or safety of the United States, the government of the U.S.A. could not see without grave concern the actual or potential possession of such harbour or other place by any government not American as to give that government practical power of control for naval or military purposes."

Bibliography.

Chapman S. "The Jungle is Neutral."
 Barber N. "The War of the Running Dogs."
 O'Ballance E. "The Communist Insurgent War."
 Thompson R. "Defeating Communist Insurgents."
 Suyin H. "And the Rain my Drink."
 Morris M. "Terrorism."
 Assegai Magazine
 Time Magazine.

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Czechoslovakia, 1968.

D.Wylie. L6.

Three times in three decades the violent overthrowal of Czechoslovakia has provided a turning-point in modern history, and each time she has emerged worse than before.

On 15th March, 1939, Adolf Hitler and the German army invaded this troublesome East European country - the first time he had violated a sovereign state. In so doing he spurred the Western camp to a resistance that was to precipitate the Second World War when he did the same to Poland in Sept. 1939. Czechoslovakia, in so far as it still existed, survived almost the entire duration of that most destructive of wars unscathed, although paradoxically Prague was the last foreign capital to remain in German hands. To the subsequent shame of the western powers Eisenhower bound his liberating armies to the Czechoslovak border, and when the Czechs appealed for Allied aid in the Prague uprising on May, 1945, General Bradley on the frontier could do nothing, the Russians could not get there on time and the revolt was crushed by the Germans. Only on the general German capitulation of 8-9th May was Prague relieved - by Soviet Russia. Thus fell into Soviet hands the last of the great East and Central European capitals, much to the chagrin of the west.

As it happened Soviet rule was not imposed immediately on Czechoslovakia. President Benes commanded a wider respect than any other governor-in-exile and his fidelity to Moscow was beyond reproach, so they left him with a government in which Communists held 38% of the votes and seven out of twenty five administrative posts. By the end on 1947 however it was clear that the Communists had lost ground and in order not to collapse completely in the forthcoming elections Klement Gottwald and the Communist Party staged a full-blooded coup d'etat.

February 1948 was no less a turning point than 1939. The coup was the end - except for Finland - of democratisation within the Soviet orbit, and was the greatest single spur to Western fears of Soviet expansion.

The years after 1948 were the blackest in Czechoslovakia's history. Its western traditions were particularly strong and it took all the more effort to uproot them. Repression was worse than in any other East European country, it was the last to experience destalinisation, and while the high tide of liberalisation in Poland and Hungary came in 1956, the first Czech thaw came only in 1962. Under the leadership of Antonin Novotny, President since 1957, liberalisation took place particularly in the economic sphere, but intellectuals still chafed under the cultural restrictions which remained. This dissatisfaction coincided with an acute leadership crisis - Novotny was not popular, particularly with the large Slovak element, and his economic experimentation was proving ruinous.

On 5th January, 1968, Novotny was replaced by Alexander Dubcek, a Slovak, as First Secretary of the Czechoslovak Communist Party (CCP) although he remained President until March. Under a new and strong liberal cabinet there ensued a period of liberalisation totally unprecedented in Soviet experience, and its coincidence with a general hardening in Soviet policies made it all the more provocative.

Liberation began with the dismissal of several of Novotny's closest supporters, including party ideologist Jin Hendrych and foreign minister Václav David, and the resignations of others followed, including that of Novotny from the Presidency - he was replaced by Ludvík Svoboda, another Liberal. As early as mid-March restrictions on writers were lifted and political prisoners released, censorship partly abolished and the sale and importation of foreign publications 'normalised', and freedom granted to Roman Catholics. On 9th April an 'Action Programme' aiming "to reform the whole political system" and to "ensure the expression of the direct will of the working people" was published. It called also for freedom of expression, recognised minority interests and limited police activity - security matters - this was Dubček's 'socialism with a humane face.'

All this, of course, was anathema to the Soviet Union and the other Socialist states. The first signs of apprehension appeared when on 26th February one Major-General Jan Sejma defected to the west and the Soviet Union sent Marshall Ivan Yakulovsky to Czechoslovakia to find if he had taken any military secrets with him - the affair led directly to the resignation of Novotny, a result which did not ease the minds of other Socialist states. Poland and Germany were particularly outspoken, being afraid that these liberal tendencies would spread.

Meetings were arranged, at Dresden on 23rd March (attended by all socialist leaders) and between Soviet and Czech leaders on 4th May, both of which stressed the need to consolidate the Socialist front and to promote "friendship and all-round co-operation between states." A Soviet military delegation was sent (at Czech invitation) to Prague on 17th May, an event which again appeared to augur well for the future. All three meetings were characterised by Czech platitudes and assurances that liberalisation offered no threat to socialist solidarity.

There is no reason to suspect the sincerity of these assurances: Dubček in particular had been brought up and educated in the Soviet Union and certainly had no wish to make a complete break with her; it is also true that liberalisation probably went further than he had originally intended. At any event the Soviets were not taken in, and in mid-May a 'war of nerves' against Czechoslovakia was initiated with military manoeuvres along her borders. On 19th May Pravda, the Soviet Communist paper, made covert references to 'right-wing liquidators' and 'lack of discipline' in un-named socialist systems, and on 11th June the Soviet Union sent their first formal protest concerning certain Czechoslovak publications. Warsaw Pact 'staff' manoeuvres, to take place in Czechoslovak, were announced - they turned out to be full-scale military exercises and the forces remained on Czechoslovak soil well over the previously announced date on such flimsy excuses as 'abnormal traffic conditions.' Pravda's attacks against Czechoslovakia's 'counter-revolutionary forces' became violently open, particularly against a document drawn up and signed by members of the Czechoslovak public and known as the "2000 Words." It called for freedom of speech and for independence - indeed it was itself a 'freedom of speech' - and precipitated a socialist reaction far in excess of its true importance. A meeting in Warsaw of all Warsaw Pact members (excluding Roumania) was convened on 14th July with the sole purpose of discussing Czechoslovakia, its result being a joint letter to the Czech government demanding the abrogation of this "absolutely

unacceptable" situation. The Czechoslovak reply hotly denied that there was any threat. Dubcek complained:

"We do not see any realistic reasons for our present situation to be called counter-revolutionary ... our alliances and friendships with the USSR and other socialist countries are deeply rooted ..."

The USSR was not satisfied. Dubcek nevertheless would not permit any return to the pre-January situation. The result was an intensification of the war of nerves: fresh manoeuvres started on 23rd July; Soviet and Polish tourists were barred from Czechoslovakia; even arms caches were planted in Czechoslovakia and attributed in the Soviet press to 'American agents and insurrectionists'; the Czech military was attacked for criticising the Warsaw Treaty command structure.

There followed two equally futile meetings in Czechoslovakia at Cienna and Bratislava on 29th July and 3rd August respectively. The first was between the Soviet Politburo and the Czechoslovak Praesidium, the second included the other socialist leaders; neither had any effect on the Czech position. A lull in the war of nerves followed Bratislava but after the visits of Ceausescu of Roumania and Tito of Yugoslavia (the two separatists) to Prague, their enthusiastic welcome and their equally enthusiastic support for the Czech liberals, Pravda renewed her attack on 16th August. On 20th August a special plenary session of the central committee of the Soviet Communist Party was convened in Moscow. That same night Soviet troops crossed the border into Czechoslovakia.

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The attack began at 11 pm. The Czech army offered no resistance. The major cities were overrun in a matter of hours. In Prague the airport was captured and Soviet aircraft began ferrying in reinforcements. The Prague Radio building was surrounded and at 6.30 went off the air. Almost at once clandestine radio stations - and even a television station - started up to keep the populace informed of the invasion's progress.

The populace itself initiated an heroic if futile show of passive resistance by removing signposts to confuse the invasion forces and even sitting down in front of advancing tanks. Clandestine printing presses put out posters faster than they could be torn down, while in Prague a number of tanks were set on fire by youths stuffing burning rags up their exhaust pipes. Wenceslas square became Prague's centre of resistance and despite the imposition of a night curfew a round-the-clock sit-down strike was started around the flag-draped statue of St. Wenceslas. Inevitably there was violence: at least 30 people were killed in the first week.

Meanwhile government buildings were occupied and Dubcek, among others, was made prisoner. Tass, the official Soviet news agency, announced that the Soviet forces had been invited by un-named members of the Czech government to 'lend assistance including military assistance.' When no Czech was found willing to collaborate the Soviets had to resort to the more doctrinaire line that Czechoslovak liberalisation was a threat to Soviet security - which it possibly was, not only politically (there had been cries in Warsaw of 'We want a Polish Dubcek') and militarily (neutralist tendencies would cause a break in Warsaw Pact defences) but also to the very positions of power of the socialist leaders themselves, and this probably underlay the whole invasion.

In any event the Soviets were unable to set up a puppet government as they had hoped - neither public approval nor President Svoboda, who went to Moscow on 23rd August, would allow the overthrow of Dubcek, and the Soviets were forced to negotiate with him. No Czech was willing to forfeit all that had been achieved in the previous eight months, but it was obvious that if Dubcek was to retain his position at all he would have to jettison some of his liberal projects, although on his return he stated there would be no turning back. However censorship was reimposed in September, and in October a Soviet-Czech treaty was signed allowing for the stationing of Soviet troops in Czechoslovakia. Gradually power was to gravitate towards those government members who inclined to the USSR and all hope for a socialist democracy behind the Iron Curtain vanished.

The immediate results of the invasion were negligible: as the Soviets had calculated the west maintained studious non-interference although they sharply denounced the invasion, and President Johnson continued to pursue his policy of east-west detente. The disturbance, as the Soviets had predicted, soon blew over but its long term implications were both un-realised by the Soviet Union and toned down by the west. The invasion had shown the true irreconcilability of eastern and western policies: the Soviets promoted disintegration in the western camp but would not tolerate the same in its own. It showed that the Soviet Union was willing to use force in a limited sphere and while it should be pointed out that force had been a last resort it was also a sign of weakness in the Soviet ideological machine. Militarily the balance of power was hardly changed but the invasion precipitated a soul-searching in NATO countries which nevertheless only resulted in a minor increase in forces offered. Europe was anxious not to alarm the USSR further; the USSR was equally eager, incidentally, to proclaim that there was no alarm. In the end however the Soviet Union must have come out stronger. Although Czechoslovakia could obviously no longer be trusted the eastern border had been consolidated and the liberal danger indefinitely averted, while there had been no counter-move from the west at all. Finally 1968 set the trend of east-west relations - mutual suspicion and, possibly, the doom of detente.

Bibliography.

Brittanica Book of the Year, 1969.
Desmond Donnelly - 'Struggle for the World'
David Thomson - 'Europe Since Napoleon'
Keesing's Contemporary Archives.

*The above article is a précis of the author's full-length monograph.

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Every year Zuro has an increased circulation and therefore a wider readership. The Editor of Zuro 1977 would welcome letters from readers, particularly those outside the school. Such letters need not be concerned directly with this year's magazine: they might relate to any aspect of history.

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